

END OF STUDIES PROJECT

Geopolitics: An Eternal Dominance

Jihene Dami

National License in Translation

Academic Year 2025-2026

Acknowledgement

This work is not at all individual; it's the essence of my professors' assistance and support, my family and friends' love and sacrifices, and my humble knowledge and passion. That being the case, I wish to express my heartfelt gratitude to them all, whose guidance, encouragement, and enduring faith have fueled my willpower to achieve this study that stands as much theirs as mine.

Foremost, I offer my sincerest thanks to my supervisor, Mr. *Mohamed Bahloul*. Their wisdom and unwavering commitment have been a constant source of inspiration and a guiding light throughout this journey. Thank you for believing in me since the very beginning, that certainly had the greatest impact on my output.

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Thanks to them I am where I'm standing today and I'm still going further.

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Personal Statement

Ever since I started pursuing my degree, I've heard the sentence "AI is replacing you" almost everyday. Being unaware of how wrong of a statement it was, fear had initially made me lose interest in the discipline and question the outcome of all efforts I'm blowing for the sake of academic excellence. Is everything I'm doing in vain? Will my degree lose its relevance for the service I am to provide is already accessible for free and is performed in seconds rather than business days? If it's the case, will I be able to pursue other professional careers as a translator? Those questions remained at the forefront of my mind until I decided to seek real answers rather than just overthink. Thus, after years of continuous research and reflection, I finally came to realize that translation is far beyond the simple act of converting words from one language to another as it is generally represented. It's a whole complex mechanism that consists of the transmission of meaning, intentions, emotions, and most importantly cultural nuances in order to enable mutual understanding between societies.

A translator is the bridge that facilitates cooperation between different nations and preserves knowledge while making it accessible across linguistic boundaries. One individual possesses a deep understanding of multiple contexts, from medicine to economy and diplomacy, an excellent command of at least two languages, and a remarkable ability to accurately adapt language according to audience and purpose, thanks to their solid ethical judgement and deep cultural awareness — qualities that remain beyond the capabilities of machines. Which brings us to conclude that, while AI systems may process vocabulary and grammar quickly, they often struggle with context, ambiguity, idiomatic expressions, humor, tone, and culturally sensitive content, making them unqualified to replace human translators. Nevertheless, it is crucial that the relation between translators and Artificial Intelligence should rather be cooperation than competition, saving the time spent on repetitive tasks while ensuring accuracy and relevance.

Furthermore, thanks to the knowledge they need to acquire in order to be able to efficiently process language in a certain context, translators are generally able to perform real tasks in the discipline they're specialized in, making them quite the versatile professionals. Which is why I had chosen Business Development as an internship subject, being passionate about it and aiming to learn more on how startups grow in real time and what impact does translation have on that field. I figured that I can actually charge such positions with the skills I got to obtain whether academically or through international organisation membership. Therefore, this project stands as proof that we will always have an unshakable role in society **as much as translators as anything else we qualify to be.**

Part I

Internship Report

INTERNSHIP REPORT

Business Development & Digital Marketing Strategy

Conducted at

DOORKNOCK PRO

Field Sales Information Management & Lead Tracking Platform

Prepared by:

Jihene Dami

Supervised by:

Mohamed Amine Guettat

Emna Ben Ayed

Internship Duration: 3 Month

Chapter I: Presentation of the Host Company

1.1 Company Overview

DoorKnock Pro is a Canadian-Tunisian software startup headquartered in Québec, Canada, specialising in field sales information management. The company develops and markets a mobile and web-based platform that provides door-to-door and field sales organisations with all the tools they need to track leads, manage territories, monitor agent activity in real time, and make data-driven decisions at every stage of the sales cycle.

The product is available on iOS, Android, and as a web portal, and is designed to serve sales teams of all sizes, from solo field representatives operating on a free plan to large enterprise organisations managing hundreds of agents across multiple territories.

At the time of my internship, the platform had recorded over one million leads collected, with active users spread across more than forty-nine countries and over seventy-four companies relying on the product daily.

1.2 The Problem DoorKnock Pro Solves

Despite the digital transformation of most business functions, the operational infrastructure supporting field and door-to-door sales teams has remained largely manual. Sales managers typically lack real-time visibility into where their agents are, what they are pitching, and how their leads are progressing. Field representatives manage their activity through paper notes, personal spreadsheets, or memory — losing prospects while duplicating effort, and missing follow-up windows with remarkable frequency.

DoorKnock Pro was designed to close this operational gap by providing an end-to-end platform that connects field activity to management visibility, transforming unstructured canvassing into a measurable, optimisable system.

1.3 Internship Context & Role

My internship at DoorKnock Pro was officially framed within Business Development, an umbrella function that, for an early-stage startup, encompasses a broad range of activities: sales outreach, partnership development, market research, content strategy, and brand positioning. Over the course of three months, my role evolved considerably from its initial definition, as I increasingly identified and prioritised structural foundations (branding, positioning, and tooling) over immediate sales activity.

Chapter II: Completed Tasks and Achieved Deliverables

2.1 Initial Plan vs. Execution Reality

At the outset of the internship, the roadmap I initially planned (check Appendix) was centred on outbound sales activity: launching cold email sequences, conducting cold calls, and building a pipeline of potential clients for the DoorKnock Pro Premium and Business packages. The assumption underlying this plan was that the product was sufficiently ready to sell, and that the primary lever for growth was volume of outreach.

Within the first few weeks, however, I encountered a set of structural obstacles that made pure outbound activity not only inefficient but potentially counterproductive. The company had no consistent visual identity. There was no unified messaging framework. The brand's digital presence was fragmented, and there were no supporting assets that could follow up a cold email or a call and do the work of converting a prospect.

I attempted to execute the original plan in parallel with raising these observations. I launched email sequences targeting sales managers in the solar, roofing, and HVAC sectors using a list of prospects gathered from Apollo.io. I conducted a number of cold calls. The results were predictably slow: low open rates, minimal responses, and zero conversions over the first six weeks. The issue was not the quality of the product, it was the absence of the brand scaffolding that sales activity requires to function.

This early experience gave me one of the most valuable lessons of the internship: that in a startup, tactical execution without strategic infrastructure is not simply inefficient, it actually actively destroys the credibility you need to eventually sell. I made the decision, in consultation with my supervisor, to redirect the majority of my effort toward building that infrastructure before resuming outbound activity.

2.2 Cold Outreach: Attempts, Learnings & Limitations

The cold outreach phase, while commercially unsuccessful, was instructive on multiple levels. I built and managed email sequences using Apollo.io, targeting decision-makers (Sales Directors, Regional Managers, and Operations leads) at companies in the D2D sales verticals.

The sequences were five-touch structures following a problem-awareness to social-proof arc, a format considered standard practice in B2B SaaS outreach.

Cold calling complemented the email sequences, primarily targeting companies that had opened emails without responding. These calls gave me a direct and unfiltered view of how potential customers perceive unsolicited pitches: most were politely dismissive, and the most common objection (often unspoken but communicated through the tone of the conversation) was a lack of familiarity with the brand. Prospects who had never heard of DoorKnock Pro, and who had no supporting material to reference after hanging up, had no rational basis for taking the next step.

The experience crystallised a structural insight: outbound sales is a trust transfer mechanism, and trust requires prior exposure to the brand. Without a consistent visual identity or any accumulated social proof, each cold interaction was starting from a deficit. This informed every subsequent decision I made during the internship.

2.3 App Localisation into Arabic: Research and Strategic Proposal

2.3.1 Genesis of the Proposal

One of the most intellectually stimulating contributions I made during the internship was entirely self-initiated. While researching market expansion opportunities for the company, I identified a significant and largely untapped potential in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region.

The D2D and field sales model is actively used in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, particularly in sectors such as telecommunications, real estate, and home services, yet the dominant field sales software tools are all English-first, with no Arabic-language support.

The Arabic-speaking market represents over 420 million native speakers, with strong concentrations in high-GDP countries (Saudi Arabia, UAE, Qatar, Kuwait...) where smartphone penetration and B2B software adoption are both accelerating. A localised Arabic version of DoorKnock Pro would not simply be a translation exercise, it would represent a genuine product differentiation in a segment where no dominant player has yet established a localised presence.

2.3.2 Research into App Localisation Techniques and Tools

The proposal required me to conduct substantial research into the discipline of app localisation — a field I had not previously studied in depth, but which I found deeply resonant with my background in translation and language sciences. App localisation (often abbreviated as L10n) goes considerably beyond the translation of user-facing text strings. It encompasses the adaptation of the product experience to the linguistic, cultural, typographic, and functional expectations of a target market.

For Arabic specifically, localisation presents a distinctive set of technical and linguistic challenges. Arabic is written right-to-left (RTL), which requires a fundamental inversion of the UI layout: navigation elements, text alignment, input fields, and iconography must all be mirrored to feel natural to an Arabic-speaking user. This is not a superficial change, it requires RTL support to be built into the application's rendering framework from a structural level, using tools such as React Native's built-in RTL support or platform-level APIs on iOS (UISemanticContentAttribute) and Android (LayoutDirection).

I researched and documented the primary tools and platforms used in professional app localisation workflows:

- **Lokalise:** a cloud-based localisation management platform that allows developers, translators, and project managers to collaborate on string translation, manage version control, and automate export to iOS (.strings), Android (.xml), and web (JSON) formats
- **Phrase (formerly Memsource):** an enterprise-grade TMS (Translation Management System) with CAT (Computer-Assisted Translation) tools, translation memory, and glossary management, widely used in software localisation projects
- **Crowdin:** a crowdsourcing-friendly localisation platform popular with open-source and startup projects, offering integrations with GitHub, GitLab, and Figma
- **i18n frameworks:** the technical standard for internationalisation (i18n), which involves extracting all hardcoded strings from source code into locale files, enabling runtime language switching without code changes
- **Unicode BIDI algorithm:** the bidirectional text algorithm that governs how RTL and LTR text coexist within the same interface, critical for mixed-language contexts

Beyond the technical dimension, I studied the cultural localisation requirements specific to Arabic markets: the use of the Gregorian calendar versus Hijri date references in formal contexts, number formatting conventions, the distinctions between Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) and Gulf colloquial dialects for UX copy, and the visual design adjustments (spacing, typography, icon semantics) that affect how Arab users perceive software quality.

This research drew heavily on my academic training in translation studies, specifically in the areas of technical translation; localisation theory; and cross-cultural communication, and constituted one of the clearest points of intersection between my educational background and my professional contributions throughout the internship.

2.3.3 The Strategic Proposal

I formalised my research into a strategic proposal for the DoorKnock Pro team. I argued that a single, well-executed localisation effort, if approached with the rigour of a professional translation project rather than a simple text swap, could open DoorKnock Pro to a market where it would face no localised competition and where the product's core value proposition (GPS tracking, territory management, lead capture, possibility of extension) maps directly onto how field sales teams already operate in Gulf markets.

The proposal was received positively and potential customers started reaching out, the sales execution was unfortunately initially interrupted by the political state in the Middle East. Whether or not the implementation re-proceeds in the short term, the exercise of producing it gave me a rare opportunity to apply translation theory, technical research, and strategic business thinking simultaneously — an experience that directly reinforced the practical value of a translation studies education in non-traditional professional contexts.

2.4 Marketing Campaign Booklet

2.4.1 Rationale

The absence of a coherent brand identity and marketing strategy was, by the midpoint of the internship, the most clearly documented obstacle to commercial progress. Rather than proposing a series of disconnected fixes, I designed and produced a comprehensive one-month marketing campaign booklet: a structured, actionable document that could serve simultaneously as a brand reference, a content calendar, a channel strategy guide, and a post-design template library.

2.4.2 Contents of the Booklet (check Appendix)

2.5 Full Business Model Document

2.5.1 Scope and Purpose

The final and most substantial deliverable of the internship was a comprehensive business model document — a strategic framework covering every dimension of DoorKnock Pro's commercial strategy. The document was intended not as a theoretical exercise but as a practical, actionable resource that the founding team could use to guide decision-making, prioritise investments, and communicate the company's strategy to potential partners and investors, or future team members.

2.5.2 Structure (check Appendix)

The document was organised across eleven sections:

Section	Content	Key Contribution
Business Overview and Value Proposition	Problem definition, product features, persona value mapping, competitive landscape	Structured DKP's positioning against 5 direct competitors with a feature-comparison table
Revenue Architecture	5 revenue streams, 3-year financial projections, unit economics model	Modelled realistic ARR trajectory from \$111K to \$1.9M over three years
Digital Marketing Strategy	8 channels with cadence, tools, budgets, and KPIs	Full channel mix with monthly budget allocations and projected ROAS per channel
Brand Architecture	Positioning, visual identity, brand asset checklist, tone of voice	Defined 'Field Sales OS' category positioning as a strategic differentiator
Growth Strategy and Sales Funnel	PLG model, funnel stages, ICP, outbound stack, viral mechanics	Designed in-app viral triggers to engineer the 'team invite' growth loop
Tools and Technology Stack	25-tool stack with costs and functions	Mapped every tool needed from content creation to revenue attribution
Investment Plan and Financial Model	3-year OpEx, break-even timeline, fundraising options, ROI by channel	Identified Month 18 break-even point with concrete milestone targets
Sustainable Development Roadmap	4-phase plan from Foundation to Dominance over 36 months	Translated strategy into concrete phase-gated actions with MRR targets
Creative Marketing Techniques	Zero-cost and paid amplification tactics, retention strategies	Identified 8 high-leverage tactics including data storytelling and franchise deals
KPIs and Governance	18-metric dashboard, weekly/monthly review cadence	Established North Star Metric (Monthly Active Paying Seats)
Risk Analysis	8-risk matrix with likelihood, impact, and mitigation	Identified platform algorithm dependency as highest-probability risk

2.5.3 Bilingual Execution

As with the campaign booklet, the business model document was fully produced in both English and French. The French version required extensive terminological work, particularly in the financial and SaaS-specific sections. The challenge of producing a French version of a document whose conceptual vocabulary is heavily anglicised (SaaS, MRR, ARR, NRR, CAC, LTV, PLG, ROAS, churn) required me to apply a dual competency: the translation knowledge to find accurate and contextually appropriate French equivalents, and the technical knowledge of the subject matter to ensure those equivalents remained meaningful to a reader with domain expertise.

I got to practice the specialized translation competencies developed during my university studies, specifically the ability to navigate terminological ambiguity and manage register and tone across languages to produce professionally appropriate target-language equivalents for technical content in a new domain. Ultimately, this dual authorship that consists of producing primary documents in English then translating them into French for a bilingual professional team was a direct, visible expression of my academic specialisation within a professional context, and one that I believe demonstrated the practical value of translation studies in fields far beyond the traditional boundaries of the discipline.

Chapter III: Critical Analysis and Professional Reflection

3.1 Sales Results: What They Actually Meant

By any conventional metric of a business development internship, the three months at DoorKnock Pro produced no measurable sales results. There were no closed deals, no converted trials, and no meaningful growth in the paying user base that could be directly attributed to my outreach efforts. I am stating this plainly because I believe it is important, both for the integrity of this report and for the intellectual honesty that academic reflection requires.

However, I would argue that the absence of sales results was not equivalent to the absence of impact, and that reframing this distinction is one of the most important analytical contributions I can make in this report. The real output of the three months was not a pipeline of closed deals, it was the identification of the structural preconditions for growth, and the production of the foundational assets that must exist before sales activity can generate compounding returns. This is a more valuable outcome than a handful of conversions built on an unstable foundation.

3.2 Understanding How Startups Actually Grow

The dominant narrative of startup growth tends to emphasise product-market fit, growth hacking, and the speed of iteration. What is less commonly discussed, and what I observed directly, is the critical role of sequencing. Before growth can be engineered, certain foundations must exist: a product that demonstrably solves a real problem (DoorKnock Pro has this), a brand that communicates that solution clearly and consistently (DoorKnock Pro lacked this when I arrived), a set of support materials that can do the work of educating and converting prospects between human touchpoints, and a data infrastructure that allows you to measure what is actually working.

The absence of foundations does not prevent activity — it is entirely possible to send emails, make calls, and post on social media without them. But it does prevent compounding. Growth compounds when each piece of activity builds on the last: a blog post generates SEO traffic, which produces email subscribers, who receive a nurture sequence, which drives trial sign-ups, which produce case studies, which close the next set of prospects. Without the infrastructure, each activity is discrete and ephemeral. With it, each activity feeds the next.

Understanding this sequencing logic, and learning to identify where it was broken, was the central intellectual contribution of the internship to my professional development.

3.3 App Localisation as a Reflection of Translational Expertise

Translation studies, as a discipline, is often perceived (including by students within it) as being primarily concerned with the conversion of text from one language to another. The localisation project demonstrated, in a concrete and commercially meaningful context, that this perception is reductive.

App localisation is, in its deepest form, a problem of equivalence — the same concept that governs translation theory, so, it requires not only linguistic competence but cultural, typographic, technical, and strategic knowledge. The research I conducted into RTL layout requirements, Unicode BIDI algorithms, different localisation management platforms, and Gulf Arabic UX conventions was an extension of my academic field into a domain that has rarely been explored in undergraduate translation curricula, and I have always believed this extension is both legitimate and necessary: the field of professional translation is expanding rapidly into software, games, apps, and digital products, and translation graduates who understand this domain will have a significant competitive advantage.

3.4 Bilingual Production: Technical Language in English & French

The most significant competency I exercised and developed during the internship was the production of technical, professional-grade documents in both English and French, covering subject matter (SaaS business strategy, digital marketing, financial modelling) that I had no prior experience documenting in either language before the internship began.

The challenges I faced in order to achieve that are, at their core, exactly the challenges that translation studies prepare students to navigate. The fact that the subject matter was business strategy rather than literary fiction or legal text does not diminish the translational complexity, if anything, it actually increases it, because errors of register or terminology in a professional document carry reputational and operational consequences.

Basically, the experience of producing and translating these documents gave me a practitioner's understanding of how translation competencies function in a workplace context. It was most definitely the application of my academic field to a real professional problem.

Chapter IV: Conclusion

This internship has significantly sharpened my sense of the professional direction I wish to pursue. The intersection of language, technology, and global market strategy — exemplified most clearly by the app localisation project — represents a field where translation expertise, business acumen, and digital literacy converge. It is a field that is growing rapidly, driven by the globalisation of software products and the increasing demand for culturally intelligent, linguistically rigorous localisation at scale.

I left this internship with a clearer understanding of my own strengths and of how those strengths can create value in contexts that would not traditionally be categorised as 'translation work'. I also left with a deep appreciation for the foundational importance of brand, language, and communication architecture in the growth of any product, lessons that I strongly believe are as relevant to my career in translation and languages as they are to the startups and technology companies where those careers increasingly unfold.

APPENDIX

The following table provides a concise reference to all primary deliverables produced during the internship, along with their format and language, and link to document:

Deliverable	Format	Language	Link
Business Development Plan	Power Point	English	Business Development
Marketing Campaign Booklet	PowerPoint	English	Mkt Camp EN
Business Model Document	Word document	English	BM Docx EN
Business Model Document (FR)	Word document	French	BM Docx FR

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ATTESTATION DE STAGE

Je soussigné, M. Mohamed Amine Guettat, Fondateur de la société **SECURAS TECHNOLOGIES**, certifie que **Mlle Jihen Dami** a effectué un stage au sein de notre entreprise dans le domaine du **Business Development et de la stratégie de marketing digital**, en tant que stagiaire, durant la période du **1er février 2026 au 15 avril 2026**.

Elle a notamment contribué à :

- La mise en place d'actions de prospection commerciale (emailing, appels à froid)
- La réflexion stratégique autour du positionnement de la solution
- La production de contenus structurants tels qu'un document de business model et un plan marketing
- L'identification d'opportunités de développement à l'international, notamment via des projets de localisation

Mlle Jihen Dami a fait preuve d'implication, d'autonomie et d'un bon esprit d'analyse tout au long de son stage. Son travail lui a permis de développer des compétences en stratégie, en communication et en environnement startup.

Le stage s'est déroulé dans de bonnes conditions générales. Nous lui souhaitons une bonne continuation dans son parcours professionnel.

Fait pour servir et valoir ce que de droit.

M. Mohamed Amine Guettat
 Fondateur – SECURAS TECHNOLOGIES
 Fait à Sfax, le 04 Mai 2026

Mohamed Amine GUETTAT

SECURAS ID A C

Part II

Article Translation

Source

De la géopolitique à la géoéconomie

Pascal LOROT

*Fondateur et co-directeur de Géoéconomie.
Président de l'Institut Choiseul.*

Paru dans la première livraison de Géoéconomie {alors appelée Revue française de Géoéconomie/ au printemps 1997, ce texte est fondateur. Il est le premier publié en France qui discute le concept de géoéconomie et pose le cadre de cette nouvelle approche des relations et conflictualités internationales.

Avec la fin de la Guerre froide, les capacités militaires des États développés ne constituent plus, de loin, le principal facteur de leur puissance sur la scène internationale. La période des conflits directs et frontaux, recourant à la puissance de feu et aux capacités militaires entre puissances industrielles est aujourd'hui révolue. Cette évolution est d'autant plus affirmée que les difficultés démographiques et la sensibilité publique des pays occidentaux ne sont plus guère favorables à l'idée de conflit^{1, 2}. La puissance s'exerce dorénavant de manière plus douce, sans recours à la coercition ;

Target

From Geopolitics to Geoeconomics

Pascal LOROT

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Published in the first issue of Geoeconomics (then called Revue française de Géoéconomie) in spring 1997, this text is foundational. It is the first published in France to discuss the concept of geoeconomics and establish the framework for this new approach to international relations and conflicts.

By the end of the Cold War, the military capabilities of developed states no longer constitute, by far, the main factor of their power on the international stage. The era of direct and frontal conflicts, resorting to firepower and military capabilities between industrial powers, is now over. This evolution is all the more pronounced that the demographic difficulties and public sensitivity of Western countries are no longer quite favourable to the idea of conflict^{1, 2}. Power is henceforth exercised in a softer manner, without recourse to coercion

elle se rapproche de ce que Joseph S. Nye a qualifié de *soft power*³.

L'ouverture des frontières, la libéralisation des échanges et les progrès de la technologie ont favorisé l'apparition de firmes multinationales dotées de stratégies mondiales. Aux côtés de leurs entreprises nationales, les États se sont engagés dans des politiques de conquête de marchés extérieurs et de prise de contrôle de secteurs d'activité considérés comme stratégiques. Au service des ambitions nationales, les diplomates doivent aujourd'hui avoir la double casquette, diplomatique et économique, ce qui n'est pas sans leur poser de problèmes⁴. De fait, la santé économique d'une nation est l'aune à laquelle on juge désormais sa puissance. Dans ce monde en train de devenir global, les intérêts économiques des nations prennent l'ascendant sur leurs intérêts politiques. Ce glissement signe l'ouverture d'une ère nouvelle, celle de la géoéconomie.

Puissance publique et géoéconomie

S'il est vrai que la conflictualité « frontale » ou classique ne prévaut plus entre pays développés, les logiques d'affrontement régissant leurs rapports n'en ont pas pour autant disparu. Seuls leur nature et leurs instruments ont changé. Désormais, en effet, lorsqu'un antagonisme il y a entre pays industrialisés, il trouve son expression pour l'essentiel sous des formes économiques.

approximating what Joseph S. Nye has called *soft power*³.

The opening of borders, trade liberalisation, and technological progress have fostered the emergence of multinational firms endowed with global strategies.

Alongside their national companies, states have engaged in policies concerning conquering foreign markets and gaining control over activity sectors considered strategic. In service of national ambitions, diplomats must today wear both a diplomatic and an economic hat, which can't be with no difficulty for them⁴.

Indeed, the economic health of a nation is now its power measure. In this world turning global, the economic interests of nations take precedence over their political interests. This shift signals the start of a new era: that of *gloeconomics*.

Public Power and Geoeconomics

If it is true that “frontal” or classical conflict does no longer prevail between developed countries, the confrontational logics governing their relations have not for that reason disappeared. Only their nature and instruments have changed. Henceforth, when antagonism exists between industrialized countries, it finds expression primarily in economic forms.

C'est là notamment la thèse que défend Edward Luttwak qui, au tout début des années 1990, annonçait l'avènement d'un nouvel ordre international où l'arme économique remplacerait l'arme militaire comme instrument au service des États dans leur volonté de puissance et d'affirmation sur la scène internationale⁵. « Les menaces militaires et les alliances ont perdu leur importance avec la pacification des échanges internationaux, précise-t-il dans son ouvrage clé *The Endangered American Dream*; dès lors, les priorités économiques ne sont plus occultées et passent au premier plan. À l'avenir, ajoute-t-il, c'est peut-être la crainte des conséquences économiques qui réglera les contentieux commerciaux, et sûrement plus les interventions politiques motivées par de puissantes raisons stratégiques. Et s'il faudra encore une menace extérieure pour assurer l'unité et la cohésion interne des nationaux et des pays, cette menace sera désormais économique ou, plus exactement, géoéconomique »⁶.

À la géopolitique classique pour laquelle les rivalités des États sont avant tout relatives à des territoires, succéderait désormais une géoéconomie révélée par l'effondrement — faute de moyens économiques suffisants — des ambitions territoriales et idéologiques de l'ancien empire soviétique et de leur corollaire, la Guerre froide.

Les objectifs de cette géoéconomie naissante ne relèvent plus, pour Edward Luttwak, de la conquête de territoires ou de l'influence diplomatique; il s'agit « de maximiser l'emploi hautement qualifié dans

This is notably the thesis advanced by Edward Luttwak who, at the dawn of the 1990s, announced the advent of a new international order by which the economic weapon would replace the military weapon as an instrument to serve the states in their will to acquire power and affirmation on the international stage⁵. “Military threats and alliances have lost their note with the pacification of international exchanges,” he specifies in his key work *The Endangered American Dream*; “henceforth, economic priorities are no longer obscured and come to the fore. Hereafter,” he adds, “it is perhaps the dread of economic consequences that will regulate trade disputes, and certainly not anymore the political interventions motivated by powerful strategic reasons. And if an external threat will still be drastic to ensure the unity and internal cohesion of nationals and countries, this threat will henceforth be economic or, more precisely, geoeconomic”⁶.

Classical geopolitics, in which state rivalries are primarily about territories, would hence yield to the geoeconomics revealed by the collapse — for lack of sufficient economic means — of the territorial and ideological ambitions of the former Soviet empire and its corollary, the Cold War. The aspirations of this nascent geoeconomics no longer pertain, for Edward Luttwak, to the conquest of territories or diplomatic influence; it is “a matter of maximising highly skilled employment in

les industries de pointe et les services à haute valeur ajoutée »⁷.

L'objectif central est de « conquérir ou de préserver une position enviée au sein de l'économie mondiale.

Qui va développer la nouvelle génération d'avions de ligne, d'ordinateurs, de produits issus des biotechnologies, de matériaux de pointe, de services financiers et tous les autres produits à haute valeur ajoutée dans les secteurs industriels, petits et grands? Les développeurs, les ingénieurs, les managers et les financiers seront-ils américains, européens ou asiatiques?

Aux vainqueurs les positions gratifiantes et les rôles dirigeants, aux perdants les chaînes de montage, à condition que leurs marchés nationaux soient assez importants et que les importations de produits déjà assemblés soient rendues impossibles par des barrières douanières »⁸.

Aujourd'hui comme hier, les États définissent puis mettent en œuvre des politiques de conquête qui trouvent désormais une traduction neuve, d'essence économique et non plus militaire mais pour lesquelles un parallélisme reste cependant possible. Le recours aux expressions militaires pour décrire les attitudes géoéconomiques est en effet caractéristique du discours d'Edward Luttwak⁹ : « les capitaux investis ou drainés par l'État sont l'équivalent de la puissance de feu; les subventions au développement des produits correspondent aux progrès de l'armement; la pénétration des marchés avec l'aide de l'État remplace les bases et les garnisons militaires

cutting-edge industries and high value-added services”⁷.

The core objective is to “conquer or preserve an enviable position within the world economy.

Who will develop the new generation of airliners, computers, biotech products, advanced materials, financial services, and all other high value-added products in industrial sectors, large and small? Will the developers, engineers, managers, and financiers be American, European, or Asian?

To the winners the rewarding positions and leading roles, to the losers the assembly lines, provided their national markets are large enough and imports of already assembled products are rendered impossible by tariff barriers”⁸.

Today as yesterday, states define and then implement conquest policies which onwards find a new expression, economic rather than military in nature, yet for which a parallel remains possible nonetheless. The use of military expressions to describe geoeconomic attitudes is indeed characteristic of Edward Luttwak's discourse⁹ : “capital invested or channelled by the state is the equivalent of firepower; subsidies for product development correspond to advances in armaments; market penetration with state assistance replaces military bases and garrisons

déployées à l'étranger, ainsi que "l'influence diplomatique".

Ces diverses activités — investir, chercher, développer et trouver un marché — sont également le lot quotidien des entreprises privées qui les exercent pour des motifs purement commerciaux. Mais quand l'État intervient, lorsqu'il encourage, assiste ou dirige ces mêmes activités, ce n'est plus de l'économie "pur sucre", mais de la géoéconomie »¹⁰

Limites et redimensionnement de la géoéconomie

L'approche développée par Edward Luttwak marque incontestablement une avancée utile à la compréhension de la nouvelle architecture internationale et du jeu de ses acteurs constitutifs.

Surtout, l'apparition de la géoéconomie en tant que concept nous paraît essentielle en ce qu'elle témoigne de l'entrée en force des questions économiques — notamment sous leur angle commercial mais pas uniquement — , dans l'agenda de la géopolitique mondiale.

En revanche, elle n'est pas exempte de critiques et d'imprécisions méthodologiques, comme par exemple s'en est fait l'écho Elie Cohen¹¹. Mais, plus fondamentalement, nous semble-t-il, l'approche d'Edward Luttwak nous paraît être trop étroite, à plusieurs titres, voire quelque peu datée pour rendre effectivement compte de la réalité économique et stratégique de cette fin de siècle.

deployed abroad, as well as 'diplomatic influence'.

These various activities — investing, researching, developing, and finding a market — are also the usual lot of private companies that carry them out for purely commercial motives. But when the state intervenes, when it encourages, assists, or directs these same activities, it is no longer 'pure' economics, it is *gloeconomics*"¹⁰.

Limits and Redimensioning of Gloeconomics

The approach developed by Edward Luttwak unquestionably marks a useful advance in understanding the new international architecture and the game of its core actors.

Above all, the emergence of *gloeconomics* as a concept seems essential to us in what it testifies to the forceful entry of economic questions — notably but not exclusively from a commercial angle — into the agenda of world geopolitics.

Alternatively, it is not free from criticism and methodological imprecision, as Elie Cohen¹¹ has noted. But, more fundamentally, it seems to us, Edward Luttwak's approach appears too narrow, on several counts, and even somewhat dated to effectively account for the economic and strategic reality of this end of century.

En premier lieu, il convient de discuter le champ d'application de la géoéconomie. Certes, cette dernière se pratique le plus souvent entre pays ayant évacué toute velléité de guerre entre eux. Elle concerne essentiellement les nations industrialisées, au premier rang desquelles les pays de la Triade (Amérique, Europe occidentale, Japon) qui se sont déchargés des vêtements de la rhétorique guerrière pour circonscrire leurs rivalités au champ économique. Mais est-il légitime pour autant de restreindre la portée de ce nouveau mode d'interprétation des rivalités de puissance aux seules nations occidentales? Plusieurs États d'Amérique latine et surtout d'Asie n'ont-ils pas su affirmer une présence forte sur la scène internationale en mettant en œuvre des stratégies que l'on peut qualifier de géoéconomiques? Les « dragons asiatiques » en sont un des exemples les plus représentatifs. Bien sûr, ils se distinguent encore des nations industrialisées d'Europe, d'Amérique et du Japon en ce qu'ils évoluent dans un champ géopolitique non maîtrisé, ce qui constitue un facteur fort de vulnérabilité. Est-ce pour autant qu'ils n'ont pas la capacité de participer effectivement aux nouvelles logiques géoéconomiques mondiales émergentes? Comment expliquer par exemple l'attractivité et les succès économiques internationaux de la cité-État de Singapour, voire même de la Corée du Sud — alors même que l'argument des bas salaires n'est plus aujourd'hui opérant —, si ce n'est, au moins partiellement,

Above all, it is relevant to discuss the scope of geoeconomics.

Certainly, the latter is most often practised between countries that have set aside any proclivity for war between them. It essentially concerns the industrialised nations, foremost among which the Triad countries (America, Western Europe, Japan), which have shed the garments of war rhetoric to confine their rivalries to the economic sphere. But is it legitimate to restrict the scope of this new mode of interpreting power rivalries to Western nations alone? Have not several states in Latin America and most of all in Asia managed to assert a strong presence on the international stage by implementing strategies that may be qualified as geoeconomic?

The “Asian dragons” are among the most representative examples. They most definitely are still distinguished from the industrialised nations of Europe, America, and Japan in that they evolve in an uncontrolled geopolitical field, which constitutes a strong factor of vulnerability.

Does this signify that they do not possess the capacity to participate effectively in the emerging new global geoeconomic logics? How else can one explain the attractiveness and international economic successes of the city-state of Singapore, or even South Korea — where the low-wage argument no longer applies today — if not, at least partially,

par la réussite d'une stratégie de conquête de parts de marché pilotée dans ces cas précis par la puissance publique. La place et le rôle de l'État dans la formulation des politiques géoéconomiques méritent eux aussi d'être questionnés.

Certes, la place de l'État est centrale dans toute stratégie géoéconomique, puisque c'est lui qui détermine les dispositifs et postures géoéconomiques, identifiant les menaces, les stratégies défensives ou offensives et les moyens à y affecter. Est-elle pour autant exclusive comme le présente implicitement Edward Luttwak? Non, car nombre d'entreprises - essentiellement les plus grandes d'entre elles, celles qui ont une visibilité suffisante aux yeux de l'État et/ou occupent un secteur considéré comme stratégique - suscitent ou peuvent susciter, directement ou non, lesdites stratégies. L'État peut agir en toute conscience, ce qui est le plus souvent le cas mais il peut aussi, dans certains cas, en quelque sorte être dupe des manœuvres initiées par une entreprise donnée pour l'inciter à mettre en œuvre une logique (d'affrontement) géoéconomique qui, in fine, bénéficiera à ladite entreprise.

En un sens, cette dernière peut aller jusqu'à « instrumentaliser » l'action de l'État dans sa stratégie d'action économique internationale. Le plus souvent, toutefois, État et entreprise agissent de concert — le premier aidant et appuyant les ambitions de la seconde —, en toute conscience des impératifs stratégiques de l'un et de l'autre.

strategy directed in these specific cases by public authority. The site and role of the state in the formulation of geoeconomic policies also deserve to be questioned.

Certainly, the state's position is central in any geoeconomic strategy, since it is the state that determines the geoeconomic arrangements and postures, identifying threats, defensive or offensive strategies, and the means to be allocated to them. But is it exclusive, as Edward Luttwak implicitly suggests? Not at all, since many firms — essentially the largest among them, those with sufficient visibility in the state's eyes and/or occupying a sector considered strategic — give or may give rise to such strategies, directly or indirectly.

The state may act in full awareness, which mostly is the case, but it also can, in certain cases, be in some sense duped by manoeuvres initiated by a given company to incite it to implement a geoeconomic (confrontational) logic which, in the end, will benefit that company.

In a sense, the latter can go so far as to “instrumentalise” the action of the state in its strategy of international economic action. Most often, however, state and company act in concert — the former aiding and supporting the ambitions of the latter — and in full awareness of each other's strategic imperatives.

Au total, le concept de géoéconomie est aujourd'hui bien plus global qu'envisagé initialement par le fondateur du néologisme; il embrasse une dimension véritablement planétaire, qui ne saurait en aucun cas se limiter aux seuls pays occidentaux.

Quelle géoéconomie?

Si l'on essaie maintenant de la définir plus précisément, nous dirons que la géoéconomie est l'analyse des stratégies d'ordre économique — notamment commercial —, décidées par les États dans le cadre de politiques visant à protéger leur économie nationale ou certains pans bien identifiés de celle-ci, à aider leurs

« entreprises nationales » à acquérir la maîtrise de technologies clés et/ou à conquérir certains segments du marché mondial relatifs à la production ou la commercialisation d'un produit ou d'une gamme de produits sensibles, en ce que leur possession ou leur contrôle confère à son détenteur — État ou entreprise « nationale » — un élément de puissance et de rayonnement international et concourt au renforcement de son potentiel économique et social.

La géoéconomie s'interroge sur les relations entre puissance et espace, mais un espace « virtuel » ou fluidifié au sens où ses limites bougent sans cesse, c'est-à-dire donc un espace affranchi des frontières territoriales et physiques caractéristiques de la géopolitique. Corollaire de cette définition,

In sum, the concept of geoeconomics nowadays is far more global than initially envisaged by the founder of neologism; it embraces a truly planetary dimension, which cannot in any case be limited to Western countries alone.

What Geoeconomics?

If we now attempt to define it more precisely, we shall say that geoeconomics is the strategies' analysis of an economic order — notably commercial — decided by states within the framework of policies aimed at protecting their national economy or certain well-identified segments thereof, at helping their “national companies” to acquire mastery of key technologies and/or to conquer certain segments of the world market relating to the production or commercialisation of a product or range of sensitive products, insofar as their possession or control confers upon its holder — state or “national” enterprise — an element of power and international influence and contributes to the strengthening of its economic and social potential.

Geoeconomics enquires into the relations between power and space, but a “virtual” or fluidified space in the sense that its limits constantly shift, that is to say a space freed from the territorial and physical frontiers characteristic of geopolitics.

A corollary of this definition:

un dispositif géoéconomique regroupera l'ensemble des instruments à la disposition d'un État, susceptibles d'être mobilisés par lui au service de la satisfaction de tout ou partie des objectifs susmentionnés qu'il s'assignerait. Enfin, dernière précision, les stratégies géoéconomiques sont le fait, le plus souvent des États développés mais peuvent, le cas échéant, être initiées par des pays industrialisés non-membres du « club occidental » pris au sens classique.

Certains peuvent être tentés de s'interroger sur les similitudes éventuelles entre géoéconomie et ce que d'aucuns nomment « guerre économique ». En fait, n'en serait-elle qu'un simple succédané ou, dit autrement, une façon plus moderne et actualisée de caractériser cette dernière?

S'il y a bien un terreau commun qui relie la « guerre économique » à la géoéconomie — la conflictualité entre partenaires associée à la conquête de parts de marché ou d'acquisitions technologiques —, là s'arrête cependant selon nous la comparaison. Au-delà du changement d'époque marqué par la fin de la période post-Guerre froide, qui incite à des évolutions sémantiques dans la description des postures et attitudes des différents acteurs de la scène internationale, plusieurs distinctions méritent d'être rappelées.

Une première distinction concerne les acteurs. Alors que des entreprises voire certains groupes d'intérêts non gouvernementaux organisés (associations de consommateurs, organisations environnementalistes, lobbies divers, etc.)

a geoeconomic apparatus will encompass all the instruments at the disposal of a state, capable of being mobilised by it in service of the satisfaction of all or part of the aforementioned objectives it assigns itself. Finally, one last precision: geoeconomic strategies are most often the work of developed states but may, where convenient, be initiated by industrialised countries that are non-members of the “Western club” in the classical context.

Some may be tempted to ask about the possible similarities between geoeconomics and what some name “economic warfare.” Is it in fact merely a substitute for it, or, put differently, a more modern and updated way of characterising the latter?

If there is indeed common ground linking “economic warfare” to geoeconomics — the conflict between partners associated with the conquest of market shares or technological acquisitions — there, in our view, the comparison ends. Beyond the shift of the era marked by the end of the post-Cold War period, which encourages semantic evolutions in the description of the postures and attitudes of the various actors on the international stage, several distinctions deserve to be recalled.

A first distinction concerns the actors. Whereas companies and even certain organised non-governmental interest groups (consumer associations, environmentalist organisations, various lobbies, etc.)

peuvent pratiquer leurs propres politiques de guerre économique, à l'échelle d'un marché national ou à un niveau planétaire, les pratiques géoéconomiques sont poursuivies par les seuls États, celles-ci étant initiées de leurs propres chefs ou en liaison étroite avec des entreprises considérées par eux comme stratégiques. Une autre différence réside dans les outils utilisés par ces mêmes acteurs.

La géoéconomie évacue à notre sens toute la rationalité guerrière de type clausewitzien sous-tendue par la notion même de guerre économique.

Certes, la stratégie géoéconomique peut reprendre certains des instruments de cette dernière (pratiques anticoncurrentielles classiques¹², utilisation discriminante de contingentement physique, des droits de douane ou d'obstacles non tarifaires¹³, réservation des marchés publics aux entreprises nationales et de certaines activités à des monopoles, sans parler de l'espionnage industriel classique) mais elle ne s'appuie généralement pas sur ses armes les plus offensives comme le recours à l'embargo unilatéral (c'est-à-dire non agréé par la collectivité internationale) ou au boycottage organisé.

Enfin, il est essentiel de souligner la relative popularité au sein de l'appareil de l'État des stratégies géoéconomiques, en ce qu'elles confèrent¹³ une nouvelle mission à ses représentants et servants (les fonctionnaires), soucieux pour ne pas dire démotivés, dans certains cas,

may pursue their own economic warfare policies, at the scale of a national market or at a planetary level, geoeconomic practices are pursued by states alone, whether initiated on their own initiative or in close synergy with companies considered strategic by them. Another distinction lies in the means used by these same actors.

Geoeconomics, in our perspective, evacuates all the Clausewitzian war rationality underlying the very notion of economic warfare.

The geoeconomic strategy may certainly adopt some of the latter's instruments (classical anti-competitive practices¹², discriminatory use of physical quotas, customs duties, or non-tariff obstacles¹³, reservation of public markets for national firms and certain activities for monopolies, not to mention classical industrial espionage) but it does not generally rely on its most offensive weapons such as recourse to unilateral embargo (one not agreed by the international community) or to organised boycotting.

Finally, it is essential to underline the relative popularity within the state apparatus of geoeconomic strategies, in that they confer¹³ a new mission on its representatives and servants (civil servants), who are concerned — not to say demotivated, in certain cases —

par les pertes relatives de souveraineté nationale liées à la globalisation et aux imbrications politico-économiques et interétatiques qui en ont découlé.

L'identification de secteurs d'activités clés ou vitaux, d'entreprises à défendre ou à promouvoir internationalement, parce que considérés comme les « champions nationaux », constituent une source renouvelée de mobilisation pour les acteurs de l'État au service des intérêts « suprêmes » du pays.

Et ce soutien apparaît d'autant plus spontané qu'il recourt à la mise en œuvre de politiques concurrentielles offensives acceptables par la communauté internationale, parce qu'affranchies des pratiques économiques les plus agressives et masquées que l'on retrouve dans ce que l'on appelle « guerre économique ».

Géopolitique et géoéconomie

À ce stade, il nous semble également important de poser en quoi la géoéconomie se différencie de la géopolitique. En premier lieu, revenons brièvement au concept de géopolitique. Héritière de l'histoire de la fin du siècle passé et de la première moitié du vingtième, la géopolitique a nourri la controverse durant plusieurs décennies avant de connaître une soudaine popularité liée à certains travaux de refondation¹⁴. Géographe et fondateur de la revue Hérodote, Yves Lacoste souligne dans le préambule du remarquable Dictionnaire de

by the relative losses of national sovereignty linked to globalisation and the political-economic and inter-state interlinkages that have resulted from it. Because they are considered “national champions,” the identification of key or vital sectors of activity of companies to be defended or promoted internationally constitutes a renewed source of mobilisation for state actors in service of the “supreme” interests of the country.

And this support appears all the more spontaneous in that it has recourse to the implementation of offensive competitive policies acceptable to the international community, because freed from the most aggressive and concealed economic practices found in what is called “economic warfare.”

Geopolitics and Geoeconomics

At this point, it also seems crucial to us to set out how geoeconomics differs from geopolitics. First, let us return briefly to the concept of geopolitics. Heir to the history of the end of the past century and the first half of the twentieth, geopolitics nourished controversy over several decades before achieving a sudden popularity linked to certain foundational works¹⁴.

Geographer and founder of the journal Hérodote, Yves Lacoste underlines in the preamble to the remarkable Dictionnaire de

Géopolitique dont il a assuré la direction, que dans « les multiples cas où l'on parle de géopolitique aujourd'hui, il s'agit en fait de rivalités de pouvoir sur des territoires et sur les hommes qui s'y trouvent; dans ces confrontations de forces politiques, ajoute-t-il, chacune d'entre elles use de divers moyens, et notamment d'arguments, pour prouver qu'elle a raison de vouloir conserver ou conquérir tel territoire et qu'inversement les prétentions de sa rivale sont illégitimes ». Plus précisément, écrit-il, « une situation géopolitique à un moment donné d'une évolution historique se définit, par des rivalités de pouvoirs de plus ou moins grande envergure, et par des rapports entre des forces qui se trouvent sur différentes parties du territoire en question»¹⁵. En définitive, la géopolitique étudie les relations de puissance entre l'homme en tant qu'acteur de son destin, l'espace et le territoire nourricier.

En d'autres termes, nous dirons que la géopolitique est une méthode particulière qui repère, identifie et analyse les phénomènes conflictuels, les stratégies offensives ou défensives centrées sur la possession d'un territoire, sous le triple regard des influences du milieu géographique, pris au sens physique comme humain, des arguments politiques des protagonistes du conflit, et des tendances lourdes et continuités de l'histoire ¹⁶.

Comme la géopolitique, la géoéconomie représente, nous l'avons vu plus haut, une méthode d'analyse et d'interprétation des rapports de force sur le plan international.

Géopolitique that he directed, that in “the many cases where people speak of geopolitics today, it is in fact a question of power rivalries over territories and its people; in these confrontations of political forces,” he adds, “each uses various means, and notably arguments, to prove that it is right to want to retain or conquer such a territory and that, inversely, the pretensions of its rival are illegitimate.”

More precisely, he writes, “a geopolitical situation at a given moment in historical evolution is defined by power rivalries of a greater or lesser scope, and by relations between forces situated in different parts of the territory in question”¹⁵.

Ultimately, geopolitics studies the power relations between man as an agent of his destiny, space, and the nurturing territory.

In other words, we shall say that geopolitics is a particular method which identifies, locates, and analyses conflictual phenomena, offensive or defensive strategies centred on the possession of a territory, under the triple lens of the influences of the geographical environment (taken in both its physical and human sense), the political arguments of the protagonists of the conflict, and the deep trends and continuities of history ¹⁶.

Like geopolitics, geoeconomics represents, as we have perceived above, a method of analysis and interpretation of power relations at the international level.

Toutefois, des distinctions fondamentales existent entre ces deux concepts.

La première différence découle de ce que la géoéconomie est avant tout le fait des États et de grandes entreprises à la stratégie mondiale, ce qui n'est pas le cas de la géopolitique puisque non seulement les États, les entreprises mais aussi les groupes humains, politiquement constitués ou non, s'appuyant sur des représentations historiques datées, participent à travers leurs actions à ces stratégies de conquête de territoires qui constituent le champ d'observation de la géopolitique.

Enfin, autre distinction essentielle, pour ne pas dire fondamentale, le but ultime des politiques géoéconomiques n'est pas le contrôle de territoires, il est d'acquérir la suprématie technologique et commerciale.

Au total, si la géoéconomie apparaît distincte de la géopolitique, ne peut-on pas dire pour autant que l'avènement de la géoéconomie marquerait la fin de la géopolitique? En d'autres termes, la géoéconomie est-elle appelée à supplanter la géopolitique à l'aube du XXI^e siècle?

La réponse est nécessairement négative.

En aucun cas, la géoéconomie ne signifie la fin des conflits et des revendications territoriales. Il n'est qu'à observer la guerre dans l'ex-Yougoslavie, les conflits en Afrique centrale, dans la région des grands lacs ou encore au Proche-Orient pour comprendre que la géopolitique en tant que méthode d'interprétation des phénomènes et rivalités de pouvoir relative à des territoires a encore de beaux jours devant elle.

Nonetheless, fundamental distinctions exist between these two concepts. The first difference stems from the fact that geoeconomics is above all the work of states and large companies with global strategies, which is not the case with geopolitics, since not only states and companies but also human groups —politically constituted or not, relying on dated historical representations— participate through their actions in these strategies of territorial conquest which constitute the field of observation of geopolitics.

Finally, another essential, not to say fundamental, distinction: the ultimate goal of geoeconomic policies is not the control of territories, it is the acquisition of technological and commercial supremacy. In sum, if geoeconomics appears distinct from geopolitics, can we say that the advent of geoeconomics would mark the end of geopolitics? In other words, is geoeconomics destined to supplant geopolitics at the dawn of the twenty-first century?

The answer is necessarily negative.

In no way does geoeconomics signify the end of conflicts and territorial claims.

One needs to only observe the war in the former Yugoslavia, the conflicts in Central Africa, in the Great Lakes region, or in the Middle East, to understand that geopolitics as a method of interpreting phenomena and power rivalries relating to territories still has bright days ahead.

En revanche, il est vrai, la validité de la géopolitique marque un recul certain dans les pays développés dès lors qu'il s'agit d'explicitier les actions et conflictualités des États occidentaux entre eux.

Certes, l'interprétation géopolitique reste utile à la compréhension d'une multitude de phénomènes essentiellement internes, par exemple les motivations d'une revendication régionale dans tel ou tel pays occidental, mais sa portée est plus limitée lorsqu'on se situe au niveau de l'État dans le cadre de ses relations avec ses partenaires industriels. Là prévaut l'approche interprétative de la géoéconomie.

Penser le monde et la puissance au XXI^e siècle

Avec la globalisation et l'ouverture des marchés et économies nationales, nous l'avons vu, l'attitude, les ambitions des acteurs mondiaux ont changé. Jusqu'alors à somme positive, le libre-échange poussé dans ses retranchements les plus ultimes par une concurrence planétaire chaque jour davantage exacerbée, est de plus en plus perçu — la perception étant peut-être plus forte que la réalité elle-même — comme étant désormais un jeu à somme nulle, où gagner une part de marché revient, de fait, à éliminer son adversaire¹⁷.

De manière davantage affirmée aujourd'hui, la conquête des marchés et la maîtrise des technologies les plus avancées ont pris le pas sur celles des territoires.

In contrast, it is true that the validity of geopolitics marks a certain decline in developed countries when it comes to explaining the actions and conflicts of Western states among themselves.

Certainly, geopolitical interpretation remains useful for understanding a multitude of essentially internal phenomena, for example the motivations of a regional demand in one or another Western country, but its reach grows narrower once the state level within the framework of its relations with its industrial partners is considered. There, the interpretive approach of geoeconomics prevails.

Conceptualizing Power in the Twenty-First Century World

With the globalisation and opening of national markets and economies, as we have seen, the attitudes and ambitions of global actors have changed.

Until then a positive-sum game, free trade, pushed to its ultimate limits by a planetary competition that grows more exacerbated day by day, is increasingly perceived — the perception perhaps being stronger than the reality itself — as being henceforth a zero-sum game, where gaining a market share amounts, in effect, to eliminating one's adversary¹⁷.

In an ever more affirmed manner today, the conquest of markets and the mastery of the most advanced technologies have taken precedence over those of territories.

C'est le cas, bien sûr pour les entrepreneurs, mais aussi, ce qui est plus nouveau, aux yeux des décideurs politiques, diplomates et autres fonctionnaires.

À cet égard, l'approche géoéconomique illustre assez fidèlement les politiques commerciales récentes des dernières administrations américaines.

La « diplomatie économique » offensive poursuivie par le président Clinton, utilisant tous les outils de la persuasion économique disponibles et où l'influence internationale des États-Unis se mesure à l'aune du nombre de marchés remportés, en représente vraisemblablement une bonne illustration. Les Européens inscrivent d'ailleurs de plus en plus leur action dans le sillon tracé par le concurrent américain: le président français se fait désormais le représentant de l'entreprise France, où qu'il se trouve, de Tokyo à Ryad en passant par Pékin ou Moscou, tandis que le chancelier allemand et le Premier ministre italien n'hésitent plus, eux non plus, à endosser les intérêts économiques et commerciaux de leurs nations respectives lors de leurs déplacements internationaux.

Même si Jean Arthuis, le ministre français de l'économie a récemment appelé ses concitoyens au « patriotisme économique »¹⁸, l'initiative reste encore à ce stade pour l'essentiel purement verbale et on est fort loin des tentatives américaines de donner une portée extraterritoriale à plusieurs de leurs législations nationales destinées à restreindre le commerce avec certains États peu en cour à Washington.

This is the case for entrepreneurs of course, it is however brand new for political decision-makers, diplomats, and civil servants.

In this regard, the geoeconomic approach does quite faithfully illustrate the recent trade policies of the last American administrations.

The offensive “economic diplomacy” pursued by President Clinton, using all available tools of economic persuasion and where the international influence of the United States is measured by the number of contracts won, most likely represents a fair illustration.

Europeans are moreover increasingly inscribing their action in the furrow traced by their American competitor: the French president now positions himself as the representative of “Corporate France”, wherever he is, from Tokyo to Riyadh via Beijing or Moscow, while the German Chancellor and the Italian Prime Minister no longer hesitate, either, to glorify the economic and commercial interests of their respective nations during their international travels.

Even if Jean Arthuis, the French Economics Minister, recently called on his fellow citizens for “economic patriotism”¹⁸, the initiative remains at this stage essentially verbal and is far eliminated from American attempts to give extraterritorial reach to several of their national laws intended to restrict trade with certain spineless states in Washington.

Dans l'ensemble, force est d'observer que les Européens accusent un retard important vis-à-vis tant des États-Unis, du Japon que de certains États — notamment asiatiques — plus petits certes, mais très présents dans certains secteurs industriels clés.

Qui plus est, s'ils ont pu commencer — bien tardivement et de manière très ponctuelle — à bâtir des schémas organisationnels de véritables stratégies géoéconomiques, l'absence de coordination à l'échelle de l'Union européenne constitue encore un lourd handicap dont ne se privent pas de tirer partie ses adversaires commerciaux.

À l'aube du XXI^e siècle, le primat nouveau des stratégies géoéconomiques dans la panoplie des instruments de politique internationale à la disposition des États marque une rupture fondamentale avec le passé. La géoéconomie ne constitue pas la fin de la puissance. Simplement, son actualité témoigne d'une nouvelle évaluation de l'importance relative des différents facteurs constitutifs de cette dernière, caractérisée notamment par la marginalisation du facteur militaro-stratégique en son sein au profit de l'économique, et de la recherche de la puissance économique comme objectif stratégique central des gouvernements occidentaux et développés. Incontestablement, l'avènement de l'approche géoéconomique porte en elle le triomphe, ou plutôt un primat certain des logiques économiques dans le concert international. Au total, la géoéconomie est aujourd'hui un phénomène planétaire,

Globally, one is forced to observe that Europeans lag significantly behind both the United States, Japan, and certain states — notably the Asian of them — smaller certainly, but very present in certain key industrial sectors.

What is more, if they have been able to start — quite belatedly and in a very piecemeal fashion — to build organisational frameworks for genuine geoeconomic strategies, the absence of coordination at the scale of the European Union still constitutes a heavy handicap that their commercial adversaries do not fail to exploit.

By the dawn of the twenty-first century, the new primacy of geoeconomic strategies in the panoply of international policy instruments available to states marks a fundamental break with the past. Geoeconomics does not constitute the end of power. Simply, its currency testifies to a new evaluation of the relative importance of the different constituent factors of the latter, characterised notably by the marginalisation of the military-strategic factor within it in favour of the economic, and the pursuit of economic power as the central strategic objective of Western and developed governments.

Unquestionably, the advent of the geoeconomic approach carries within it the triumph, or rather a certain primacy, of economic logics in the international concert. In sum, geoeconomics today is a planetary phenomenon,

représentant un nouvel espace de compétition entre nations marchandes développées.

Elle apparaît également comme une méthode d'analyse de l'action internationale des principales puissances notamment occidentales.

Dans un monde où les puissances se cherchent de nouveaux champs de manœuvre, l'approche géoéconomique offre une grille de lecture insurpassable des relations internationales.

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representing a new space of competition between developed trading nations.

It also appears as a method of analysis of the international action of the principal powers, notably Western ones.

In a world where powers seek new fields of manoeuvre, the geoeconomic approach offers an unsurpassable reading grid of international relations.

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1. Notamment ceux coûteux en vies humaines. Voir le débat sur la guerre à «zéro mort» aux États-Unis.

2. À tel point, si l'on en croit certains analystes des relations internationales, que la plupart des pays riches auraient même perdu toute volonté de puissance, leurs populations n'aspirant plus qu'au confort matériel et au maintien d'un niveau de vie économique supérieur à celui du reste du monde. C'est là notamment la thèse défendue par Pascal Boniface dans son dernier ouvrage. Voir *La volonté d'impuissance. La fin des ambitions internationales et stratégiques?*, Seuil, 1996.

3. Joseph S. Nye, Jr., *Le leadership américain*, PUN, 1992.

4. Reginald Dale, "Diplomats: Don't Forget the Economy", *International Herald Tribune*, 26 novembre 1996.

5. Edward Luttwak, "From Geopolitics to Geo-economics. Logics of Conflict, Grammar of Commerce", *The National Interest*, Été 1990; *The Endangered American Dream*, Simon Et Schuster, 1993, traduction française, *Le rêve américain en danger*, Odile Jacob, 1995. Dans cet ouvrage qui fit grand bruit aux États-Unis, il dénonce un Japon qui ne respecterait pas les règles du libre-échange mondial et ne jouerait pas sur le terrain de la compétition économique le jeu du marché. L'affrontement nippo-américain, selon lui, est essentiellement d'ordre stratégique et politique en ce que les pratiques commerciales déloyales japonaises portent atteinte à la sécurité des États-Unis.

6. Edward Luttwak, *Le rêve américain en danger*, Odile Jacob, 1995, p. 40.

7. *Ibid*, pp. 41-42.

8. *Ibid*, p. 403.

1. Particularly those costly in human lives. See the debate on "zero-casualty" war in the United States.

2. To this very extent, if certain analysts of international relations are to be believed, that most rich countries have even lost all will to power, their populations aspiring only to material comfort and the maintenance of an economic standard of living superior to the rest of the world.

This is notably the thesis defended by Pascal Boniface in his last book. See *La volonté d'impuissance. La fin des ambitions internationales et stratégiques?*, Seuil, 1996.

3. Joseph S. Nye, Jr., *Le leadership américain*, PUN, 1992.

4. Reginald Dale, "Diplomats: Don't Forget the Economy", *International Herald Tribune*, 26 November 1996.

5. Edward Luttwak, "From Geopolitics to Geo-economics. Logics of Conflict, Grammar of Commerce", *The National Interest*, Summer 1990; *The Endangered American Dream*, Simon & Schuster, 1993, French translation, *Le rêve américain en danger*, Odile Jacob, 1995. In this work which caused great controversy in the United States, he denounces a Japan that would not respect the rules of world free trade and would not play by market rules in economic competition. The Japanese-American confrontation, according to him, is essentially of a strategic and political order in that Japan's unfair trade practices damage the security of the United States.

6. Edward Luttwak, *Le rêve américain en danger*, *Odile Jacob*, 1995, p. 40.

7. *Ibid*, pp. 41-42.

8. *Ibid*, p. 403.

9. Edward Luttwak formalise son approche en des termes « militaires » offensifs: « En géoéconomie, comme à la guerre, les armes offensives dominent. Parmi elles, la recherche développement (R&D), dopée par le soutien des États et l'argent des contribuables, est d'une importance capitale.

De même qu'à la guerre l'artillerie conquiert, par la force de son feu, le terrain qu'occupera ensuite l'infanterie, de même la R&D peut conquérir le terrain industriel de demain en permettant d'assurer une supériorité technologique décisive (...). L'artillerie de la recherche-développement encouragée par l'État est cruciale, mais il faut aussi prêter assistance à l'infanterie, c'est-à-dire au secteur productif(...). La dernière arme offensive, c'est la «finance prédatrice». Si l'artillerie de la recherche-développement n'arrive pas à conquérir les marchés par le simple biais de la supériorité technologique, si les subventions de fonctionnement octroyées d'une façon ou d'une autre s'avèrent insuffisantes, on peut parvenir à exporter, même avec de très puissants concurrents, en offrant des prêts au-dessous des taux du marché » , op. cit., pp. 399 à 402.

10. *Ibid*, p. 34.

11. Dans *La tentation hexagonale. La souveraineté à l'épreuve de la mondialisation*, Fayard, 1996, Elie Cohen critique certaines thèses d'Edward Luttwak en s'interrogeant notamment sur les similitudes entre mercantilisme et géoéconomie ainsi que sur les justifications de son appel à la « course aux armements géoéconomiques ». Voir pp. 133 à 135.

12. Ententes, abus de position dominante ou de dépendance économique, pratiques restrictives de concurrence, contrefaçon de marques ou d'idées ...

13. Règles techniques ou sanitaires, par exemple.

14. Pour une analyse détaillée de la genèse de la géopolitique et de ses différentes interprétations historiques et politiques, voir Pascal Lorot, *Histoire de la géopolitique, Economica*, 1995.

9. Edward Luttwak formalises his approach in “offensive” military terms: “In geoeconomics, as in war, offensive weapons dominate. Among them, research and development (R&D), boosted by state support and taxpayers’ money, is of capital importance.

Just as in war artillery conquers, by the force of its fire, the terrain that infantry will then occupy, so R&D can conquer the industrial terrain of tomorrow by ensuring a decisive technological superiority (...).

The artillery of state-encouraged research and development is crucial, but one must also lend assistance to the infantry, that is to say the productive sector (...).

The last offensive weapon is ‘predatory finance.’ If the artillery of research and development does not manage to conquer markets by the simple means of technological superiority, if operating subsidies granted in one way or another prove insufficient, one can manage to export, even with very powerful competitors, by offering loans below market rates”, op. cit., pp. 399 to 402.

10. *Ibid*, p. 34.

11. In *La tentation hexagonale. La souveraineté à l'épreuve de la mondialisation*, Fayard, 1996, Elie Cohen criticises certain theses of Edward Luttwak by questioning notably the similarities between mercantilism and geoeconomics as well as the justifications for his call for a “geoeconomic arms race.” See pp. 133 to 135.

12. Agreements, abuse of dominant position or economic dependence, restrictive trade practices, trademark or intellectual counterfeiting...

13. Technical or sanitary rules, for example.

14. For a detailed analysis of the genesis of geopolitics and its various historical and political interpretations, see Pascal Lorot, *Histoire de la géopolitique, Economica*, 1995.

15. Yves Lacoste (sous la direction de), *Dictionnaire de géopolitique*, Flammarion, 1993.

16. Voir Pascal Lorot et François Thual, *La géopolitique*, Clefs-Montchrestien, 1997.

17. Les disparitions massives d'entreprises et les regroupements dans certains secteurs clés comme l'aéronautique, la construction automobile ou encore l'électronique illustrent parfaitement cette situation.

18. Interview *Le Figaro*, 6 janvier 1997.

15. Yves Lacoste (ed.), *Dictionnaire de géopolitique*, Flammarion, 1993.

16. See Pascal Lorot and François Thual, *La géopolitique*, Clefs-Montchrestien, 1997.

17. The massive disappearance of companies and consolidation in certain key sectors such as aeronautics, automobile manufacturing, and electronics perfectly illustrate this situation.

18. Interview *Le Figaro*, 6 January 1997.

Part III

Translation Commentary

TRANSLATION COMMENTARY

Pascal Lorot, “De la géopolitique à la géoéconomie”

French → English · Analytical Commentary

I. INTRODUCTION: THE TRANSLATION TASK NATURE

This commentary accompanies the performed English translation of Pascal Lorot’s founding article, “*De la géopolitique à la géoéconomie*”, originally published in the inaugural issue of the *Revue française de Géoéconomie* in spring 1997 and reprinted in the summer 2009 issue of *Géoéconomie*. The text is no simple academic article: it is a programmatic manifesto and a neologism-defining act, an intertextual argument woven around extensive quotation from Edward Luttwak’s English-language work. This hybrid nature — simultaneously theoretical, polemical, definitional, and journalistic — does indeed generate a translation challenge of exceptional complexity, demanding competencies that cut across multiple disciplines: political science, economics, military history, French rhetorical tradition, and Anglo-American academic discourse conventions. The full translation of this text is the first of its kind, and the main aim behind choosing it, beside many other reasons that are to be revealed through the commentary, is to address different difficulties one can face when translating a text of this nature from the source to the target language. I tried, by achieving this commentary, to proceed systematically through the principal categories of translation difficulty, from the macro-level (register, genre, and discourse structure) to the micro-level (individual lexical choices, syntactic transpositions, and paratextual elements). Particular attention was paid to the terminological core of the text: the concept of geoeconomics itself, whose very untranslatability in certain registers constitutes one of the article’s central arguments. Quotations from the source text and their English renderings are reproduced throughout for analytical clarity, following the convention: [SL] for the source-language passage and [TL] for the target-language rendering. It should be noted from the outset that the original text was itself written in the shadow of translation. Lorot’s central theoretical interlocutor, Edward Luttwak, published his foundational geoeconomic argument in English in 1990, and the French edition of *The Endangered American Dream - Le rêve américain en danger* - was available by 1995. Lorot quotes extensively from the French translation of Luttwak, which means that a certain portion of the commentary below concerns my obligation as a translator to assess whether back-translating Lorot’s French quotations of Luttwak produces an acceptable English rendering, or the original English source should instead be sought directly. Thus, the question of translation mediation — French as an intermediate language between an English source and an English target — is one of the subtlest challenges this text poses

II. GENRE, REGISTER, AND DISCOURSE ARCHITECTURE

2.1 The Genre Problem: Between an Academic Article and the Political Manifesto

Lorot's text occupies an unstable generic position that profoundly conditions every translation decision. It is simultaneously an academic journal article (with footnotes, third-person narration, and systematic argumentation) and a foundational manifesto (it invents, or at least introduces to the French academy, the term 'géoéconomie' as a technical concept). This bi-character means that constant register calibration is crucial: too domesticated into contemporary Anglo-American academic prose, and the text loses its historical urgency and intellectual assertiveness; too foreignized, and it reads as alien or stilted.

French academic writing in social sciences traditionally tolerates a degree of rhetorical embellishment and authorial voice that is markedly higher than its Anglo-American counterpart. Where an English author might write 'it can be argued that', Lorot writes 'nous dirons que' ('we shall say that') — assertive, declarative, even oracular!

I had to make a systematic choice between preserving this elevated register and normalising it for English readers who expect a more hedged, hypothetical academic mode. Throughout this translation, the decision was taken to preserve Lorot's assertive tone, since to do otherwise would not merely alter stylistic texture but totally misrepresent the intellectual confidence that characterises the founding gesture of a new discipline.

2.2 French Sentence Architecture versus English Prose Rhythm

The French academic prose in the tradition Lorot inhabits is characterised by long, architecturally complex sentences in which subordinate clauses multiply, participial constructions accumulate, and the main verb is frequently delayed by layers of qualification. English academic prose, by contrast, prefers shorter syntactic units, a more direct subject-verb-object sequence, and a preference for coordination over subordination. This fundamental divergence in prose architecture means that the translation must not simply be a transfer of French sentences into English intact: doing so would produce prose that is grammatically valid but rhythmically alien to an English reader.

Consider the following representative sentence from the opening paragraph:

SL: *Cette évolution est d'autant plus affirmée que les difficultés démographiques et la sensibilité publique des pays occidentaux ne sont plus guère favorables à l'idée de conflit.*

TL: *This evolution is all the more pronounced that the demographic difficulties and public sensitivity of Western countries are no longer very favourable to the idea of conflict.*

The construction ‘d’autant plus... que’ is a correlative comparative of reinforcement that has no precise single lexical equivalent in English. ‘All the more... that’ is the conventional rendering. It however produces a slightly formal, almost legalistic tone that the French original does not carry to the same degree. ‘The more so because’ is an alternative that is crisper yet risks sounding dated. Deciding between formal equivalence (preserving the correlative structure) and dynamic equivalence (normalising to a contemporary English idiom), the choice is ultimately an interpretive one. The decision therefore landed on the first option for it preserves the author’s tone better.

2.3 The ‘Nous’ of French Academic Discourse

One of the most persistent structural challenges throughout the text is the use of the first-person plural pronoun ‘nous’, which operates in a fundamentally different way in French academic discourse than its English equivalent. In French, ‘nous’ serves simultaneously as an authorial ‘we’ (a single author speaking with collegial authority), a rhetorical device of reader inclusion, and occasionally a genuine plural referring to the editorial collective. Expressions such as ‘nous l’avons vu’, ‘nous semble-t-il’, and ‘nous dirons que’ pepper the article.

In contemporary English academic writing, the authorial ‘we’ — while not extinct — is considerably less common and can strike readers as either pretentious or confusingly plural. The most natural English rendering typically moves between ‘we’ (when the original is clearly inclusive or collegial) and constructions that foreground the argument rather than the author, such as ‘it seems’ or ‘as has been seen’. This leaves us to multiple options that include but are not limited to: ‘we shall say’ that preserves the authoritative, almost legislative quality of Lorot’s voice; ‘let us say’ that democratizes it; ‘it may be said’ that hedges it; and ‘I shall argue’ that individualises it. We may note that each option produces a subtly different implied relationship between author, text, and reader. The choice depended on my personal view of what aspect to emphasize in each context.

III. THE TERMINOLOGICAL CORE: ‘GÉOÉCONOMIE’ AND ITS CONCEPTUAL FIELD

3.1 Translating a Neologism in the Act of Its Creation

The cardinal terminological challenge of this text is the word ‘géoéconomie’ itself. The article is the founding document of the concept’s French reception: Lorot isn’t translating an established term but crystallising a nascent discourse. The fact that Luttwak had already used ‘geo-economics’ in English (in his 1990 National Interest article ‘From Geopolitics to Geo-economics’) adds a layer of irony to this translation project: the English term predates the French one, so, by translating the French text, we’re in a sense returning a concept to its language of origin.

The primary decision is orthographic: ‘geoeconomics’ (without hyphen, as a fully naturalised compound) versus ‘geo-economics’ (hyphenated, preserving the morphological transparency of the prefix) versus ‘geo-economy’ (which would be a calque of the French ‘géoéconomie’ as a count noun). My choice of ‘geoeconomics’ — unhyphenated, as a mass noun — follows the convention established in contemporary English-language international relations scholarship, where the term has been fully absorbed into the discipline’s lexicon. Luttwak himself vacillated between hyphenated and unhyphenated forms. The decision is not merely cosmetic: the hyphen preserves the neologistic quality of the term (drawing attention to its composite nature), while the solid compound signals full lexical integration.

géoéconomie *géoéconomie (fr.)* → *geoeconomics (en.)*

A mass noun denoting both the phenomenon and the discipline of analysis. The French term functions both as a concrete noun (‘la géoéconomie existe’) and as an abstract field name (‘la géoéconomie est une méthode’).

English ‘geoeconomics’ replicates this double function. The alternative ‘geo-economy’ would suggest a specific economic geography of a place rather than a mode of geopolitical analysis — an institutional False Friend (Faux Ami).

3.2 The Geopolitics/Geoeconomics Binary and Its Terminological Consequences

Lorot’s entire argument is structured around a conceptual binary: ‘géopolitique’ (geopolitics) versus ‘géoéconomie’ (geoeconomics). This opposition is not merely terminological but additionally ontological, as it claims to describe a historical rupture in the nature of international conflict. It is pivotal to ensure that the terminological system is internally consistent throughout, since any variation in the rendering of these terms risks undermining the argument’s logical coherence. ‘Géopolitique’ presents less difficulty than ‘géoéconomie’ since ‘geopolitics’ is a fully established English term.

However, the fact that the French word functions both as a proper noun designating the academic discipline and as a common noun designating a set of practices was considered. Lorot writes ‘la géopolitique classique’ — ‘classical geopolitics’ — where ‘classical’ carries a periodising function (pre-Cold War) that risks being confused with a normative evaluation (‘the classical school of geopolitics’). The choice of ‘classical’ over ‘traditional’ or ‘conventional’ was deliberate: it signals historical depth without condescension.

3.3 ‘Conflictualité’: An Untranslatable Abstract Noun

Among the most technically demanding individual terms in the text is ‘conflictualité’, which appears in the formulation ‘la conflictualité «frontale» ou classique ne prévaut plus entre pays développés’ and again in ‘le terreau commun qui relie la «guerre économique» à la géoéconomie — la conflictualité entre partenaires’. This term is a French abstract noun derived from ‘conflictuel’ (conflictual) that has no precise single-word English equivalent.

SL: *S’il est vrai que la conflictualité « frontale » ou classique ne prévaut plus entre pays développés...*

TL: *If it is true that ‘frontal’ or classical conflict does no longer prevail between developed countries...*

The solution adopted — rendering ‘conflictualité’ as ‘conflict’ — is the most natural English equivalent, although it entails a semantic loss. In French, ‘conflictualité’ is an abstract mass noun denoting the state, quality, or regime of being conflictual, the general disposition toward conflict, the structural presence of conflict as a mode of relation, rather than any specific instance of conflict. ‘Conflict’ in English can serve as a mass noun (‘the potential for conflict’) but primarily functions as a count noun (‘a conflict’, ‘the conflict’). The nuance that Lorot is describing a systemic disposition rather than discrete events is partially occluded in the English rendering. Alternative options considered included ‘conflictuality’ (a rare but existing English abstract noun used in critical theory, which would preserve the morphological parallel, but sounds academic to the point of opacity) and ‘confrontational logic’ (more explanatory but syntactically unwieldy in context).

3.4 ‘Puissance’: The Central Lexical Knot

I would say no single term in this text presented a more sustained difficulty than ‘puissance’. It appears in a variety of combinations: ‘volonté de puissance’, ‘puissance publique’, ‘puissance de feu’, ‘facteur de leur puissance’, ‘rapports de force’, and many others. The semantic field of ‘puissance’ in French straddles three English words — ‘power’, ‘strength’, and ‘capacity’ — without mapping cleanly onto any of them.

puissance *puissance (fr.)* → *power / capacity / might (en.)*

In geopolitical discourse, ‘puissance’ most closely corresponds to ‘power’ as used in International Relations theory (the ability to achieve desired outcomes on the international stage). However, ‘power’ in English is more individuated and more readily count-plural (‘the great powers’) than the French ‘puissance’, which retains a more abstract, almost philosophical character when used in the singular. ‘Puissance de feu’ → ‘firepower’ (a technical military compound that works idiomatically); ‘volonté de puissance’ → ‘will to power’ (already established in English from Nietzsche, which Lorot’s usage deliberately echoes); ‘facteur de puissance’ → ‘factor of power’ rather than the more idiomatic yet less precise ‘power factor’ (which in engineering refers to electrical efficiency).

Particularly treacherous is the phrase ‘volonté de puissance’, used in the expression ‘dans leur volonté de puissance et d’affirmation sur la scène internationale’. This phrase deliberately echoes Nietzsche’s ‘Wille zur Macht’ — will to power — which makes the canonical philosophical source of the expression. In French, the echo is natural; Nietzsche’s work entered French political discourse through multiple channels and the phrase carries both its philosophical resonance and a more general political-strategic meaning. In English, ‘will to power’ is howbeit so strongly anchored to Nietzschean philosophy that its use in a geopolitical analysis creates a jarring register shift. The most ideal choice was to render the phrase as ‘will to power and affirmation on the international stage’, preserving the Nietzschean echo, since it seems likely Lorot intended it, albeit this decision requires the reader to navigate an implicit philosophical allusion that the French original handles more smoothly.

3.5 ‘Puissance Publique’: Another Institutional False Friend

The term ‘puissance publique’ merits specific attention for it is an institutional term of art in French public law that operates as a partial false friend in translation.

In French administrative and constitutional law, ‘la puissance publique’ designates the formal sovereign authority of the state — the legal capacity to act with binding authority over individuals and entities, including through administrative acts that do not require the consent of those bound. It is distinct from the state as a political entity (‘l’État’) and from the government as an executive organ (‘le gouvernement’).

SL: *La place et le rôle de l’État dans la formulation des politiques géoéconomiques... une stratégie de conquête de parts de marché pilotée dans ces cas précis par la puissance publique.*

TL: *...a market-share conquest strategy directed in these specific cases by public authority.*

The rendering of ‘puissance publique’ as ‘public authority’ is defensible, yet, it still isn’t entirely satisfactory. ‘Public authority’ in English denotes any body exercising public functions and can refer to sub-state entities (local authorities, regulators), which risks diluting the sovereign, centralised character of ‘puissance publique’.

‘State authority’ is more accurate but sounds bureaucratic in context. ‘Government’ would be the most idiomatic choice but loses the constitutional depth of the original. We ultimately prioritised contextual readability, using ‘public authority’ when the institutional character is foregrounded and ‘the state’ when the political entity is primary.

IV. MILITARY REGISTER AND THE GRAMMAR OF COMMERCIAL CONFLICT

4.1 Luttwak’s Military Lexicon and Its Re-translation

A substantial portion of the article consists of extended quotations from Luttwak’s work, mediated through the French translation. This creates a unique translation problem: Deciding whether to back-translate Lorot’s French rendering of Luttwak’s English, or to seek Luttwak’s original English formulations. The scholarly and ethical obligation points toward the latter wherever the original is traceable. Nevertheless, Lorot’s own framing of Luttwak’s argument is itself an interpretive act — he selects, condenses, and paraphrases, which means that even where Luttwak’s English is available, the French quotation in Lorot’s text may not be a literal translation of it, but rather an adaptation serving Lorot’s argument.

The most sustained example of this problem is the long passage in footnote 9, in which Lorot cites Luttwak’s extended military analogy comparing geoeconomic instruments to weapons of war. The passage uses technical military vocabulary (‘artillerie’, ‘infanterie’, ‘armes offensives’, ‘feu’) translated from Luttwak’s English through the French intermediary. Ideally, this should be rendered back into an English that is both faithful to the argument and natural as military register prose.

SL: *De même qu’à la guerre l’artillerie conquiert, par la force de son feu, le terrain qu’occupera ensuite l’infanterie, de même la R & D peut conquérir le terrain industriel de demain...*

TL: *Just as in war artillery conquers, by the force of its fire, the terrain that infantry will then occupy, so R&D can conquer the industrial terrain of tomorrow...*

The parallel simile construction ‘de même que... de même’ (just as... so) is formally preserved in the translation. The challenge lies in the military vocabulary: ‘terrain’ in French military usage means both ‘ground’ (physical) and ‘terrain’ (tactical space), and the industrial extension ‘terrain industriel’ exploits this double sense. ‘Industrial terrain’ in English preserves the metaphorical extension somewhat awkwardly; ‘industrial ground’ would be more naturally military but loses the abstract geographical sense. ‘Industrial landscape’ would domesticate the image entirely.

I retained ‘industrial terrain’ as the least-poor compromise, privileging semantic transparency over idiomatic fluency.

4.2 ‘Armes Offensives’ and the Clausewitzian Vocabulary

Lorot’s distinction between geoeconomics and ‘guerre économique’ (economic warfare) is grounded partly in a Clausewitzian framework, which the text invokes explicitly: ‘la géoéconomie évacue à notre sens toute la rationalité guerrière de type clausewitzien’.

The adjective ‘clausewitzien’ is a derived form of the proper noun ‘Clausewitz’ that operates in French academic discourse as a recognised shorthand for a particular theory of conflict — the idea that war is the continuation of policy by other means, and that strategic logic governs all forms of organised conflict. The translator’s use of ‘Clausewitzian’ preserves this reference directly, as the term is equally established in English International Relations discourse.

More subtle is the recurring use of ‘offensif’ and ‘défensif’ as applied to geoeconomic strategies. In French, ‘stratégie offensive’ and ‘stratégie défensive’ are technical terms in both military and business strategy, and their use in this text deliberately bridges the two registers. The English equivalents ‘offensive’ and ‘defensive’ carry the same double register and translate without significant loss. However, ‘logiques d’affrontement’ — a key phrase in the text — requires more care.

logiques d’affrontement *logiques d’affrontement (fr.) → confrontational logics (en.)*

‘Affrontement’ in French carries a stronger physical charge than its English cognate ‘confrontation’: it implies a face-to-face collision, a direct clash, something more visceral than the diplomatic hedging that ‘confrontation’ can suggest in English. ‘Confrontational logics’ preserves the structural character of the original but slightly domesticates its intensity. ‘Logics of clash’ would be more literal but sounds abrupt. The plural ‘logics’ (rather than ‘logic’) is deliberate: it follows the usage in French social science discourse of ‘logiques’ as designating distinct, co-existing structural rationalities within a system.

4.3 ‘Pénétration des Marchés’: A commercial Military Metaphor

The phrase ‘pénétration des marchés avec l’aide de l’État’ encapsulates one of the text’s most characteristic rhetorical moves: the systematic application of military-territorial vocabulary to commercial phenomena. ‘Pénétration’ in commercial French is a standard term (part of the phrase ‘taux de pénétration’, market penetration rate), but in this context its military etymology is intentionally foregrounded by Lorot/Luttwak as part of the extended military analogy. The English ‘market penetration’ functions exactly as the French does: as a naturalised commercial term whose violent origin is normally suppressed. Thus, the translation preserves the same deliberate double meaning.

Similarly, ‘conquête de marchés extérieurs’ (conquest of foreign markets) and ‘prise de contrôle de secteurs d’activité considérés comme stratégiques’ (seizure of control of sectors of activity considered strategic) deploy territorial and military vocabulary in commercial contexts. ‘Conquest’ in English is the appropriate rendering of ‘conquête’ here, and it is no more

metaphorically jarring in English than in French, since both languages have normalised the vocabulary of commercial warfare to a comparable degree.

V. SYNTACTIC AND RHETORICAL CHALLENGES

5.1 The ‘D’autant Plus... Que’ Construction

The correlative comparative ‘d’autant plus... que’ is among the most frequently recurring and syntactically formidable constructions in French academic argumentation. It functions as a scalar reinforcement marker, indicating that one proposition intensifies another. As noted in the introduction to this commentary, ‘all the more... that’ or ‘all the more... in that’ are the standard English renderings, but neither captures with precision the scalar logic of the original. The construction appears at least three times in this relatively short text, and each instance requires a slightly different solution depending on context. In ‘Cette évolution est d’autant plus affirmée que les difficultés démographiques...’ the standard rendering is appropriate. In ‘ce soutien apparaît d’autant plus spontané qu’il recourt à la mise en œuvre de politiques concurrentielles offensives acceptables’, the chain of subordination is more complex, requiring the sentence restructuring to avoid an English construction of unwieldy length.

SL: *Ce soutien apparaît d’autant plus spontané qu’il recourt à la mise en œuvre de politiques concurrentielles offensives acceptables par la communauté internationale, parce qu’affranchies des pratiques économiques les plus agressives et masquées que l’on retrouve dans ce que l’on appelle « guerre économique ».*

TL: *And this support appears all the more spontaneous in that it has recourse to the implementation of offensive competitive policies acceptable to the international community, because freed from the most aggressive and concealed economic practices found in what is called “economic warfare”.*

The translation reproduces the French sentence’s complexity, the English result is however syntactically strained: the participial absolute ‘freed from’ is grammatically valid but requires the reader to supply the implicit subject (‘policies’) across a clause boundary. This makes an instance where complete restructuring (breaking the sentence into two) might produce a smoother English prose, but at the cost of the rhetorical momentum of the original, where the single long sentence enacts the comprehensive, encompassing quality of Lorot’s argument.

5.2 Negation with Concession: ‘Ne... Pas Pour Autant’

The construction ‘ne... pas pour autant’, meaning ‘not for that reason’ or ‘not thereby’, is a marker of concessive negation that appears multiple times in the text: ‘n’en ont pas pour autant disparu’, ‘ne peut-on pas dire pour autant que’, ‘ne signifie pas pour autant’.

This construction expresses a logical restraint: it denies that a previously stated consequence follows from a previously stated cause. It therefore is a characteristic tool of French academic argumentation that distinguishes careful reasoning from sweeping assertion.

English has several equivalents: ‘for that reason’, ‘thereby’, ‘as a consequence’, ‘on that account’. However, none operates as idiomatically and elegantly in English as ‘pour autant’ does in French. ‘The logics of confrontation governing their relations have not for that reason disappeared’ — the adopted rendering — is formally correct but has a slightly archaic, Latinate flavour (‘for that reason’ approaching ‘propterea’). ‘Nonetheless, this does not mean that the confrontational logics have disappeared’ would be more natural but adds a clause and shifts the rhetorical weight.

5.3 Nominalisations and the Abstract Noun Cascade

French academic prose, following a tradition rooted in the grand style of the Académie française, shows a marked preference for abstract nominalisations where English would prefer verbal or adjectival constructions. Lorot’s text exemplifies this tendency throughout.

Consider the following passage, which chains several abstract nouns in rapid succession:

SL: *...caractérisée notamment par la marginalisation du facteur militaro-stratégique en son sein au profit de l'économique, et de la recherche de la puissance économique comme objectif stratégique central des gouvernements occidentaux et développés.*

TL: *...characterised notably by the marginalisation of the military-strategic factor within it in favour of the economic, and the pursuit of economic power as the central strategic objective of Western and developed governments.*

The phrase ‘au profit de l'économique’ is particularly interesting. ‘L'économique’ is a substantivised adjective — the economic (dimension/sphere/factor) — used as a mass noun. This construction is fully grammatical in French (‘le politique’, ‘le social’, ‘le culturel’ are all established substantivised adjectives in French social science discourse) but has no natural English parallel. ‘The economic’ as a freestanding noun phrase in English is technically possible but sounds marked and theoretical. The ultimate choice was to retain it — ‘in favour of the economic’ — as a deliberate echo of the French, trusting that the specialist readership of a journal of geoeconomics would recognise the usage.

In a more general audience text, the phrase would indeed need expansion: ‘in favour of economic factors’ or ‘in favour of economic over military considerations’.

5.4 ‘Voire’: Translators’ Perennial Enemy

The French adverb ‘voire’ is one of the most persistent small-scale challenges in French-to-English translation, precisely because its exact logical function is context-dependent in ways that resist a single systematic English equivalent. In contemporary French usage,

‘voire’ expresses a scalar escalation: ‘or even’, ‘indeed even’, ‘and perhaps more so’, that adds a further degree to a previously stated proposition. However, it also carries an occasional nuance of sceptical qualification, close to ‘indeed’ when used ironically.

SL: ...l'approche d'Edward Luttwak nous paraît être trop étroite, à plusieurs titres, voire quelque peu datée pour rendre effectivement compte de la réalité économique et stratégique de cette fin de siècle.

TL: ...Edward Luttwak's approach appears too narrow, on several counts, and even somewhat dated to effectively account for the economic and strategic reality of this end of century.

The choice of ‘and even’ for ‘voire’ is standard in formal translation and is appropriate here. However, I would like to state that ‘voire’ in this context carries a slightly disparaging tone — the suggestion that Luttwak’s work is not only narrow but actually out of date — that ‘and even’ reproduces only partially. ‘Indeed, somewhat dated’ would have added the necessary critical edge but disturbed the sentence’s rhythmic structure. This is an instance of what translation theorists call a ‘micro-loss’: a small but cumulative sacrifice of tone for the sake of syntactic coherence.

VI. LEXICOLOGICAL ANALYSIS: KEY TERM CLUSTERS

6.1 The Field of Power and Influence

The text is saturated with a dense lexical field relating to power, influence, and international standing. Several terms within this field present systematic translation hardships because they are near-synonyms in French that map onto the same English word, requiring the translator to mark distinctions through context and paraphrase rather than through distinct vocabulary.

rayonnement *rayonnement (fr.)* → *influence / prestige / international standing (en.)*

‘Rayonnement’ literally denotes the act of radiating (light, heat) and is used metaphorically in French to denote the diffusion of cultural, political, or economic influence. It is an inherently positive term (one ‘rayonnes’ when one projects attractive power outward) and its closest English equivalent is ‘influence’, though this loses the radiating, emanating quality of the original. ‘Prestige’, ‘standing’, and ‘reach’ are contextually appropriate alternatives.

The term appears in the key definitional sentence: ‘confère à son détenteur [...] un élément de puissance et de rayonnement international’ → ‘confers upon its holder [...] an element of power and international influence’. The decision to use ‘influence’ rather than ‘prestige’ was motivated by the economic-strategic context: ‘prestige’ in English has become associated with superficiality in foreign policy discourse (the ‘prestige project’ pejorative), while ‘influence’ retains analytical neutrality.

affirmation *affirmation (fr.)* → *assertion / affirmation / self-assertion (en.)*

The phrase ‘volonté de puissance et d'affirmation sur la scène internationale’ uses ‘affirmation’ in the sense of the active projection and assertion of national identity and interest on the world stage — the act of making oneself count, of being recognised as a significant actor. The English ‘affirmation’ is a false friend here: it primarily denotes the positive

assertion of a proposition or of one's identity in a psychological sense. 'Self-assertion' would be more accurate but introduces a psychological register absent from the French. Although 'Assertion' is more rendering in context; 'affirmation of one's presence on the international stage' is the fully transparent alternative.

6.3 Market and Commercial Vocabulary

The commercial vocabulary in the text is broadly standard and presents fewer translation difficulties than the geopolitical lexicon, but several phrases deserve comment.

SL: *conquérir certains segments du marché mondial relatifs à la production ou la commercialisation d'un produit ou d'une gamme de produits sensibles*

TL: *to conquer certain segments of the world market relating to the production or commercialisation of a product or range of sensitive products*

'Gamme de produits' is a standard commercial French expression (equivalent to 'product range' or 'product line') that translates readily. More interesting is the use of 'sensibles' — literally 'sensitive' — applied to products.

'Produits sensibles' in French trade policy discourse designates categories of goods that are politically or strategically sensitive (agricultural products, armaments, hi-tech goods subject to export controls). The English term 'sensitive products' exists in international trade law with a similar meaning, making this an instance of parallel technical vocabulary that translates without loss. Meanwhile, the term is less familiar to general English-speaking audiences than to specialists, which generated the temptation to gloss it — 'strategically sensitive products' — which was ultimately resisted in favour of preserving the compactness of the original.

6.4 'Pur Sucre' — Idiomatic Opacity

One of the most distinctively idiomatic passages in the entire text is the conclusion of Luttwak's definition of geoeconomics, as rendered by Lorot:

SL: *Mais quand l'État intervient, lorsqu'il encourage, assiste ou dirige ces mêmes activités, ce n'est plus de l'économie « pur sucre », mais de la géoéconomie.*

TL: *But when the state intervenes, when it encourages, assists, or directs these same activities, it is no longer 'pure' economics, it is geoeconomics.*

The expression 'pur sucre' — literally 'pure sugar' — is a French colloquial intensifier meaning 'the real thing', 'completely pure', 'unadulterated'. It functions adjectivally and has a slightly ironic, conversational register that stands out sharply against the surrounding formal academic prose. The idiomatic English equivalent would be 'the genuine article', 'pure and simple', or 'in its pure form'. The translation rendered it as 'pure' (with quotation marks to preserve the ironic register of the original), sacrificing the colourful specificity of 'pur sucre' for readability.

An alternative translation ('it is no longer economics, pure and simple') would have been more idiomatically natural and would have preserved some of the colloquial flavour, but would have equally introduced an expression ('pure and simple') that is itself something of a cliché in English.

VII. INTERTEXTUAL CHALLENGES AND QUOTED MATERIAL

7.1 The Problem of Back-Translation from Luttwak

As noted in the introduction, a significant portion of this text consists of passages from Luttwak's *The Endangered American Dream*, quoted via the French translation *Le rêve américain en danger* (Odile Jacob, 1995). This created a methodological problem of serious complexity: as the translator of Lorot's text, should I reproduce the passages as Lorot cites them (i.e., translate the French rendering back into English), or seek Luttwak's original English formulations?

The ethical and scholarly imperative favours using Luttwak's English originals wherever they can be traced. Nonetheless, the practical reality is that the French translation used by Lorot may not be a strict literal translation of the English original (French translators of Luttwak may have made their own interpretive choices) and Lorot's own selective quotation and paraphrase of the French text may have introduced further distance from the English original.

The outcome is that a 'clean' back-translation to Luttwak's English is often not achievable, and the most that can be done is to render the French passage in accurate English that corresponds as closely as possible to Luttwak's documented positions. This epistemological limitation is not solely a technical inconvenience: it raises a deeper question about the nature of translation as intellectual mediation.

When Lorot quotes Luttwak in French, he is engaging with a mediated version of the American scholar's thought. The English translation of Lorot thus operates at a third remove from Luttwak's original intuition. Each act of translation is an act of interpretation, and the cumulative effect of this chain of interpretive translations is that Luttwak's argument as it appears in this text is, in a fundamental sense, Lorot's Luttwak — a version shaped by the French translator's choices and Lorot's own editorial selections.

7.2 The Quotation Marks System: « » versus ‘ ’

French uses guillemets (« ») as its primary quotation mark, with different functions than the English double inverted commas. In this text, Lorot employs guillemets for three distinct

purposes: direct quotations from external sources (Luttwak), conceptual terms used with a degree of ironic or definitional distancing («guerre économique», «champions nationaux», «pur sucre»), and the author's own formulations that he wishes to highlight as technical coinage («géoeconomie» in its first definitional uses).

The English translation necessarily collapses this three-way distinction into a single system of double inverted commas, which means that a degree of differentiation is lost. Where the French guillemets signal 'I am quoting this term with some critical distance', the English double quotes can appear ambiguous — is this a quotation, a neologism, or an ironic usage?

I addressed this partially by varying the framing language ('what is called', 'so-called', 'in the terminology of') but the underlying semiotic distinction between the French and English quotation systems cannot be fully replicated.

7.3 Nietzsche, Clausewitz, and Embedded Intellectual Echoes

The text is threaded with implicit philosophical and strategic allusions that operate differently in French and English intellectual contexts. As discussed above in the section on 'puissance', the phrase 'volonté de puissance' carries a Nietzschean resonance that is arguably even more potent in the French tradition, where Nietzsche was extensively debated in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries and his vocabulary penetrated political science, than in the English tradition, where it is associated primarily with academic philosophy.

Similarly, the reference to 'rationalité guerrière de type clausewitzien' is legible to any political scientist in either language, but 'Clausewitzian war rationality' has a more marked, technical sound in English than the more normalised French 'type clausewitzien'. I retained both allusions intact, judging that the specialist readership of the journal would be equipped to receive them, for domesticating them would impoverish the text's intellectual texture.

VIII. CULTURAL AND CONCEPTUAL MEDIATION

8.1 'La Triade' and Area-Specific Economic Vocabulary

The term 'la Triade', used in the phrase 'les pays de la Triade (Amérique, Europe occidentale, Japon)', is a concept from international political economy popularised by Kenichi Ohmae in the late 1980s to designate the three dominant economic blocs of the post-Cold War world. The term was in wide use in French economic and geopolitical discourse in the mid-1990s when Lorot wrote this article, but was considerably less standardised in English, where 'the Triad' exists as a technical term but is not universally familiar to general academic readers.

I chose to reproduce “the Triad” (capitalised, with the parenthetical gloss retained) as the clearest option; adding an explanatory note might have been warranted for a non-specialist audience.

8.2 ‘Dragons Asiatiques’ — Temporal Cultural Referent

The phrase ‘dragons asiatiques’ — Asian dragons or Asian tigers — is a journalistic and economic shorthand for the high-growth East Asian economies (South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore) that was in active use in the 1990s. The metaphor was more prevalent in French than in English usage, where ‘Asian tigers’ was the more common equivalent. I rendered this as “Asian dragons” in quotation marks, preserving the French metaphor rather than substituting the English “tigers”, since both terms are understood in context and the French original’s specific choice of ‘dragons’, with its connotations of power and mythological force, is worth preserving.

8.3 ‘Entreprise France’ and Journalistic Neologism

The phrase ‘entreprise France’, rendered in the translation as ‘Corporate France’ — is a journalistic coinage that Lorot uses without quotation marks in the original, suggesting that it was sufficiently established in French public discourse in 1997 to require no special marking. The concept (France as a national commercial enterprise, with the President as its chief salesman) has parallels in English journalistic vocabulary (‘Brand Britain’, ‘UK plc’), and ‘Corporate France’ was chosen as the most natural English equivalent, carrying the implication of top-level executive representation without the more ideologically loaded connotations of ‘France Inc’.

8.4 ‘Patriotisme Économique’ and the Limits of Calque

The expression ‘patriotisme économique’ — economic patriotism — was used by the French Economics Minister Jean Arthuis in a January 1997 interview with *Le Figaro*, and Lorot cites it as an example of an emerging geoeconomic rhetoric in French political discourse. The expression is a direct calque in both French and English, and ‘economic patriotism’ translates without difficulty. It however has to be taken into consideration that the cultural and political valence of ‘economic patriotism’ differs between the two languages: in French, it was a relatively new term with a positive, mobilising charge; in Anglo-American discourse, it had already acquired protectionist connotations in some quarters, associated with ‘buy American’ campaigns. The translation preserves the neutrality of the original by reproducing the term directly and trusting the context to govern its interpretation.

IX. MORPHOLOGICAL AND DERIVATIONAL CHALLENGES

9.1 Adjectives Derived from Proper Nouns

The text makes extensive use of adjectives derived from proper nouns, a common feature of French academic discourse: ‘clauswitzien’, ‘nietzschéen’ (implied), ‘soviétique’, ‘nippon-américain’. These present no significant translation problem in most instances, as English academic vocabulary contains the same derived adjectives (‘Clausewitzian’, ‘Soviet’, ‘US-Japan’). However, the compound ‘nippon-américain’, a standard French formation combining the Nippon-derived prefix ‘nippon-’ with ‘américain’, requires a slightly different approach in English, where ‘US-Japan’ or ‘American-Japanese’ are more natural than ‘Nippo-American’. It was more suitable to use ‘Japanese-American’ as the most transparent and neutral rendering.

9.2 The Prefix ‘Géo-’ and Its Derivational Productivity

One of the most linguistically interesting features of this text is the derivational productivity of the prefix ‘géo-’ in French, which Lorot exploits to generate a structured conceptual family: ‘géopolitique’, ‘géoéconomie’, ‘géoéconomique’, ‘géoéconomiquement’ (implied). This prefix system works with equal efficiency in English: ‘geopolitics’, ‘geo-economics’, ‘geo-economic’, which makes the terminological core of the text unusually well-suited to translation.

The derived adjective ‘géoéconomique’ translates directly to ‘geo-economic’, and the nominal form ‘géoéconomie’ to ‘geo-economics’, preserving the disciplinary parallel with ‘geopolitics/géopolitique’ that is central to Lorot’s argument. This terminological symmetry across the two languages is, from a translation perspective, a rare and fortunate coincidence.

9.3 Substantivised Infinitives and Gerund Constructions

French readily substantivises infinitive verb forms to create abstract nouns (e.g., ‘le savoir’, ‘le pouvoir’, ‘l’être’), a construction that has no equivalent in English. This text uses a variant of this construction in the phrase ‘la conflictualité «frontale» ou classique ne prévaut plus entre pays développés, les logiques d’affrontement régissant leurs rapports n’en ont pas pour autant disparu’: here ‘régissant leurs rapports’ is a present participial clause used adjectivally, which in English requires a relative clause (‘which govern their relations’) that adds a word and slightly changes the rhetorical rhythm.

X. PARATEXTUAL ELEMENTS AND EDITORIAL CONVENTIONS

10.1 The Footnote System

The text's eighteen footnotes range from simple bibliographic references to extended argumentative glosses (notably footnote 9, which contains a long passage from Luttwak). The translation preserves the footnote system intact, including the bibliographic references in their original French form (author, title, publisher, date) supplemented by English translations of titles where appropriate. French bibliographic conventions differ from English ones in several minor respects (the order of elements, the use of italics, the capitalisation of titles) but these differences are of editorial rather than linguistic significance. More substantive is the treatment of footnote references that include critical commentary on other scholars (notably Elie Cohen's critique of Luttwak in footnote 11). These paratextual arguments are integral to the article's academic positioning and must be translated with the same care as the main text. The challenge here is to preserve the precise nature of the academic critique (Cohen's specific objections to Luttwak's similarities with mercantilism) without expanding or contracting it beyond what the French original supports.

10.2 The Journal Footer

The footer 'GÉOÉCONOMIE | Été 2009' presents a small translation decision:

'Été' means 'Summer', and the journal's title 'Géoéconomie' is retained untranslated (as it is the title of the journal, not a common noun). The footer is rendered as 'GÉOÉCONOMIE | Summer 2009' in the translation, preserving the title in French while translating the season. This mirrors standard practice for the translation of journal articles, where journal names are treated as proper nouns and left in their original language — a translation aspect that I wanted to shed light on.

10.3 The Title

The title 'De la géopolitique à la géoéconomie' deserves brief commentary. The preposition 'de... à...' expresses directional movement (from... to...) and implies a historical progression, a transition from one era or episteme to another. 'From Geopolitics to Geoeconomics' is the natural and most literal English rendering and was adopted. The alternative 'From Geopolitics to Geo-economics' (hyphenated) was rejected as inconsistent with the unhyphenated form used throughout the translation. 'Beyond Geopolitics: The Rise of Geoeconomics' would be a more Anglo-American academic title convention but would introduce an interpretive bias not present in the source.

CONCLUSIONS: FUNDAMENTAL CHOICES

This commentary has traced the principal translation difficulties encountered in rendering Pascal Lorot's foundational article into English, proceeding from the macro-level of genre and register through the intermediate level of syntax and rhetoric to the micro-level of individual lexical and morphological choices. Several overarching conclusions may now be drawn.

First, the text's terminological core — the concept of 'géoéconomie' — translates with unusual directness into English, a fact that is partly explained by the concept's Anglo-American origins. The English 'geoeconomics' was available as a rendering from the outset, and the parallel terminological architecture of the 'géo-' prefix family in both languages made systematic terminological consistency achievable without significant semantic loss. This is a rare advantage in translation work, and I tried to exploit it fully. **Second**, the structural and rhetorical divergences between French and English academic prose (the French preference for long, subordinated sentences, abstract nominalisations, scalar markers, and authoritative first-person assertion) required systematic, context-sensitive management throughout. Indeed, no single solution is applicable to all instances of these divergences; each requires a judgment about the relative priority of fidelity to source-text form, naturalness in the target language, and preservation of the author's rhetorical voice. **Third**, the text's status as a partially re-translated text, quoting Luttwak's English via a French intermediary, creates an irreducible epistemological complexity that no translation can fully resolve. The decision I took to render the French quotations of Luttwak into natural English (rather than seeking Luttwak's original formulations in every case) is defensible as a practical measure, as I believe the reader of the translation will mostly be aware that these passages represent Lorot's Luttwak, mediated through French, rather than Luttwak's direct voice. **Fourth**, this commentary has attempted to demonstrate that translation commentary is not merely an inventory of problems and solutions, it is a form of close reading in its own right. To translate a text is to read it with unusual intensity, attending to every shade of meaning, every syntactic nuance, every cultural presupposition that the author's language encodes. The difficulties catalogued above are not failures of the translation, they are features of the source text, evidence of the richness and complexity of Lorot's scholarly French. This as well serves as an evidence on how demanding French to English translation actually is, foremost for the faced difficulties are not exclusively the mentioned ones.

I would finally state, to sum up, that an outstanding translation, in the truest sense, is not one that conceals these difficulties but one that engages with them honestly, making its choices visible and accountable to the reader who is equipped to evaluate them.

AI VS. HUMAN TRANSLATION

I. Paragraph Choice

Of all the passages in Lorot's article, one stands apart in the density and diversity of its translation demands. It is the central definitional paragraph from the section entitled "Quelle géoéconomie?" in which the author offers his formal, systematic definition of the very concept around which the entire article is organised. I therefore selected it as the subject of the present comparison for it is syntactically the most complex, terminologically the richest, and in which the entire intellectual stakes of the article are concentrated.

THE SOURCE PARAGRAPH

SOURCE TEXT

Si l'on essaie maintenant de la définir plus précisément, nous dirons que la géoéconomie est l'analyse des stratégies d'ordre économique – notamment commercial –, décidées par les États dans le cadre de politiques visant à protéger leur économie nationale ou certains pans bien identifiés de celle-ci, à aider leurs « entreprises nationales » à acquérir la maîtrise de technologies clés et/ou à conquérir certains segments du marché mondial relatifs à la production ou la commercialisation d'un produit ou d'une gamme de produits sensibles, en ce que leur possession ou leur contrôle confère à son détenteur – État ou entreprise « nationale » – un élément de puissance et de rayonnement international et concourt au renforcement de son potentiel économique et social. La géoéconomie s'interroge sur les relations entre puissance et espace, mais un espace « virtuel » ou fluidifié au sens où ses limites bougent sans cesse, c'est-à-dire donc un espace affranchi des frontières territoriales et physiques caractéristiques de la géopolitique.

THREE DIFFERENT TRANSLATIONS

NAIVE AI TRANSLATION

If we now try to define it more precisely, we will say that geoeconomics is the analysis of economic strategies — particularly commercial ones — decided by states within the framework of policies aimed at protecting their national economy or certain well-identified parts of it, at helping their "national companies" to acquire mastery of key technologies and/or to conquer certain segments of the world market related to the production or commercialization of a product or a range of sensitive products, in that their possession or control gives its holder — state or "national" company — an element of power and international influence and contributes to strengthening its economic and social potential. Geoeconomics questions the relations between power and space, but a "virtual" or fluid space in the sense that its boundaries are constantly moving, i.e. a space freed from the territorial and physical borders characteristic of geopolitics.

INFORMED AI TRANSLATION

If we now attempt to define it more precisely, we shall say that geoeconomics is the analysis of strategies of an economic order — notably commercial — decided by states within the framework of policies aimed at protecting their national economy or certain well-identified segments thereof, at helping their “national companies” to acquire mastery of key technologies and/or to conquer certain segments of the world market relating to the production or commercialisation of a product or range of sensitive products, in that their possession or control confers upon its holder — state or “national” enterprise — an element of power and international influence and contributes to the strengthening of its economic and social potential. Geoeconomics enquires into the relations between power and space — but a “virtual” or fluidified space in the sense that its limits constantly shift, that is to say a space freed from the territorial and physical frontiers characteristic of geopolitics.

HUMAN TRANSLATION

If we now attempt to define it more precisely, we shall say that geoeconomics is the strategies’ analysis of an economic order — notably commercial — decided by states within the framework of policies aimed at protecting their national economy or certain well-identified segments thereof, at helping their “national companies” to acquire mastery of key technologies and/or to conquer certain segments of the world market relating to the production or commercialisation of a product or range of sensitive products, insofar as their possession or control confers upon its holder — state or “national” enterprise — an element of power and international influence and contributes to the strengthening of its economic and social potential. Geoeconomics enquires into the relations between power and space, but a “virtual” or fluidified space in the sense that its limits constantly shift, that is to say a space freed from the territorial and physical frontiers characteristic of geopolitics.

II. Side by Side Comparison

1. “Nous dirons que”: The Assertive Register of the Author’s Voice

In French academic discourse, especially of the programmatic kind that characterises a founding manifesto, “nous dirons que” is not a tentative statement of intent; it is a solemn, almost legislative declaration, closer in English to the formal future of common law (“we shall say”) than to the casual predictive future (“we will say”). The difference between “will” and “shall” is one that most English speakers have ceased to hear, but in formal academic and legal prose, the latter carries the weight of a definition being laid down, a category being established, or a name being given. This marks the difference between describing an intention and performing an act.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** “we will say that” — register neutralised, legislative force lost.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** “we shall say” — register correctly recovered via prompt instruction.
- ▶ **Human:** “we shall say” — recovered through recognition of French academic assertive mode.

2. “Pans bien identifiés”: Partitive Precision

The noun “pans” is a partitive noun in French that denotes a sector of a larger whole, with a slight spatial or structural connotation (a “pan” of a wall is a face or section of it). In political economy discourse, “pans de l’économie” is an established phrase meaning “sectors of the economy”. Naive AI renders this as “certain well-identified parts”, which is correct but imprecise, too uncountable to carry the institutional weight the French word bears. Informed AI uses “segments,” which is an improvement but loses the structural quality of “pans”. I retained “segments,” accepting it as the least-bad English rendering while acknowledging that the full connotative range of the original is not fully preserved.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** "parts" — too generic; loses structural register.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** "segments" — more precise, but structural connotation still reduced.
- ▶ **Human:** "segments" — same choice, but consciously adopted with documented awareness of the micro-loss.

3. “Entreprises nationales” in Guillemets: The Scare Quote Problem

Lorot places “entreprises nationales” in guillemets (« ») throughout the article, and this paragraph is no exception. In French, guillemets perform multiple functions: quotation, citation, and — crucially here — what might be called “distancing irony”, a signal that the author is using a term that belongs to a particular discourse or ideology without fully endorsing it. In this case, they serve as a signal that the term is used by states in their own ideological framing of economic competition and not a neutral analytical category. All three translations render the guillemets as English double quotation marks (“”), which is the standard conversion. However, I would explicitly address the loss entailed by this conversion: French guillemets carry a visual and typographic distinctiveness that English double quotes do not, and the triple function they perform collapses in English into a single ambiguous marker that can be read as irony, special terminology, or simple direct quotation.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** Converts « » → " " mechanically, no awareness of triple function.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** Converts correctly but the ironic-distancing function is not foregrounded.
- ▶ **Human:** Converts correctly; the semiotic loss is documented and theorised in the commentary.

4. “En ce que”: The Precision of the Causal Subordinator

The subordinating conjunction “en ce que” is among the most precise logical connectives in formal French prose. It introduces a clause that specifies the condition by virtue of which the preceding statement holds, distinct from the simpler “parce que” (because, causal) and from “étant donné que” (given that, explanatory). In this sentence, the expression specifies the criterion by which a product qualifies as “sensible”: it is not merely causal but definitional. Both naive and informed AI render this as “in that,” which is technically correct, but also is the weakest possible choice, since “in that” in English can function as a mere explanatory subordinator rather than as a definitional criterion. I chose “insofar,” knowing that it limits a statement, indicating that something is true or possible only up to a specific point, which is nearly what the context here demands. I believe it is the most defensible English rendering of a connective that is more logically precise in French than any available English equivalent allows.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** "in that" — correct form, no awareness of its limitation.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** "in that" — correct, guided by contextual prompt.
- ▶ **Human:** "insofar" — chosen knowingly as best available; limitation documented.

5. “Puissance et rayonnement international”: The Untranslatable Doublet

The paired nouns “puissance et rayonnement international” constitute a semantically rich and resistant passage. “Puissance” is the central term of the article, and its challenges have been discussed at length in the translation commentary. “Rayonnement” presents a different order of difficulty: it is a noun derived from the verb “rayer” and denotes the diffusion of influence, prestige, or authority outward from a centre. In French cultural and political discourse, “rayonnement” is a term with a long and valorised history: the “rayonnement de la France” is a concept central to French foreign policy self-understanding since at least the nineteenth century. No English word captures this precisely. “Influence” is the closest functional equivalent but loses the radiating, emanating, outward-projecting quality of the original. “Prestige” is too passive. “Reach” is too tactical. Naive and informed both AI choose “international influence,” which is acceptable but flat. I retained it as the most rational choice, aware of why it is a compromise, and how the surface forms may converge while the depth of understanding diverges dramatically.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** "power and international influence" — acceptable, no awareness of the cultural depth of rayonnement.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** "power and international influence" — prompted to correct register, residual loss unaddressed.
- ▶ **Human:** "power and international influence" — same surface form; depth of loss theorised in commentary.

6. “Espace fluidifié”: The Neologism Decision

Perhaps the single most revealing moment of difference between the three approaches occurs with the neologism “espace fluidifié” — literally “fluidified space”. This is a coinage: “fluidifié” is not a standard dictionary entry but a participial adjective derived from the verb “fluidifier”, which itself is a technical neologistic formation. Lorot is constructing a concept — a space whose limits have been deliberately or structurally made to flow rather than to stand fixed. Naive AI renders this as “fluid space”, which, although smoother and more natural in English, is not a translation at all: it is a domestication that converts a coined participle into a simple adjective. The distinction is philosophically significant: “fluidified” implies transformation, the space did not start fluid; it was made fluid by the forces of globalisation that geoeconomics theorises. Informed AI, responding to the instruction to preserve the neologism, renders “fluidified space”, which sounds unusual in English but is technically correct. I accordingly retained the expression since a neologism in the source should produce a corresponding coinage in the target.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** "fluid space" — domestication: the process and agency of fluidification erased.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** "fluidified space" — neologism preserved when explicitly instructed.
- ▶ **Human:** "fluidified space" — preserved through theoretical understanding of why neologisms must not be normalised.

7. “Frontières territoriales et physiques”: Geopolitical Register in a Single Word

The final phrase of the paragraph turns on the word “frontières”. In French, “frontière” means both “border” and “frontier”, these are not equivalent in English, particularly in the context of geopolitical theory: “Border” denotes the administrative and legal line of demarcation between two states, while “Frontier” in the geopolitical tradition carries a richer set of connotations, suggesting the zone of contact between political entities. Naive AI uses “borders,” being the more common and natural English word. Informed AI, with contextual instruction, uses “frontiers”, which is the choice I opted for as well for Lorot’s argument is about the territorial imagination of geopolitics, so “frontiers” carries that imagination where “borders” does not.

- ▶ **Naive AI:** "borders" — more common, but loses the geopolitical-theoretical register.
- ▶ **Informed AI:** "frontiers" — recovered through contextual instruction about IR discourse.
- ▶ **Human:** "frontiers" — chosen through understanding of the geopolitical tradition Lorot invokes.

III. Conclusion

The preceding dissection is not an exercise in finding fault with machine translation. The naive AI version of this paragraph is a competent piece of work: it is grammatically correct and semantically adequate for a general reader, effectively able to capture the essential propositional content of the original. If the goal of translation was just a transfer of information, the naive AI version would pass. Translation is however way deeper than that. It is the transfer of meaning in the fullest sense, covering tone, register, institutional context, cultural resonance, philosophical implication, and the precise logical structure that the author chose as the vehicle for their argument.

The comparison between naive and informed AI is equally instructive. The informed AI version is, in most respects, superior to the naive one, but its superiority is entirely conditional on the quality of the instruction it received. Every improvement in the informed AI version is traceable to an explicit prompt as it cannot generate these instructions itself. It indeed is a powerful tool. But the intelligence that directs it is not its own. This points to the most fundamental distinction between human and machine translation: A human translator makes every choice knowingly. They know what they are sacrificing when they sacrifice it and can account for it. A machine translation system makes choices probabilistically, selecting the most likely target-language token sequence given the source-language input and its training distribution. It has no theory of what is at stake in the choice, while the human translator has nothing but a theory.

There is a further dimension that no comparison of translated paragraphs can fully capture: the relationship between the paragraph and the whole. In order to produce the version analysed above, I had read the entire article, translated it completely, written an eleven-section analytical commentary on its translation challenges, and composed a closing chapter of a thesis in which the intellectual content of the article was brought into dialogue with lived professional experience. Thus, my translation suggestion of this paragraph is not a paragraph in isolation; it is an expression of a comprehensive, theorised understanding of the entire text. The machine translates paragraphs. **I translate arguments.**

This is not a defence of human translation as uniformly superior or of machine translation as uniformly inferior. For high-volume translation tasks, current AI systems produce outputs that are adequate for most practical purposes, and the economics of the profession have irrevocably shifted as a result. But the question posed by this paragraph is not a question about adequacy. It is one about whether the meaning has been genuinely understood and genuinely conveyed. And that question, for this paragraph and for every paragraph likewise, remains **irreducibly human.**

Part IV

Closing Chapter

Closing Chapter

Words Must Understand The World

I. FROM THE FIELD TO THE TEXT: A Moment of Reflection

There is a particular kind of silence that descends on a sales meeting when geopolitics enters the room uninvited. That silence made the space where this thesis was born.

During my internship in Business Development, I suggested promoting and selling our product to clients and prospects across the Middle East, one of the most compelling and most demanding markets in the world. The sales team started a campaign that served as an act of trust built across differences: negotiations conducted not only between companies but between worldviews, institutional cultures, and expectations shaped by entirely distinct histories. We started seeing real potential in the new market.

And then Iran struck.

The geopolitical tremors that followed were immediate and far-reaching. Gulf states recalibrated their diplomatic postures overnight. Client contacts in the region went quiet, not out of disinterest, but out of a rational and entirely understandable priority reassignment: when one's immediate geography has become a theatre of open interstate conflict, the acquisition of a product, however valuable, is not the most pressing matter.

From a purely commercial standpoint, this was a setback. From an intellectual standpoint however, it was a revelation — or rather, a corroboration of something that theory states plainly but experience makes visceral and undeniable: Geopolitics is not a backdrop to economic life. It is not a contextual variable to be noted in the footnotes of a business report and then set aside. It actually is the substrate on which all economic activity rests, the invisible grammar of every international transaction, the hidden architecture of every supply chain — big or small, every market entry strategy, and every bilateral negotiation.

The Iranian strikes did not merely delay a sales cycle: they made vividly apparent the degree to which every commercial relationship that crosses a national border is simultaneously a geopolitical relationship.

It was in this frame of mind, charged with a practical and lived understanding of the stakes involved, that I encountered Pascal Lorot's foundational article, "De la géopolitique à la géoéconomie". The text felt, from the very first reading, less like a scholarly article and more like a map of the territory I had just been navigating.

Lorot's central argument — that the end of the Cold War did not end interstate rivalry but merely displaced it from the military to the economic sphere, so states now pursue through commercial and financial instruments what they once pursued through armies — was not an abstract proposition for me. It was a description of what I had lived: a business development strategy rendered temporarily inoperable by the calculations of sovereign states pursuing interests that had nothing to do with, and cared nothing for, the particular commercial negotiation I had been conducting.

The choice of this text for translation was therefore not arbitrary, not merely the product of a bibliographic search for an untranslated French source of sufficient academic standing. It was a choice motivated by the conviction that understanding the relationship between geopolitics and economics is not a luxury reserved for statesmen and strategists. It is a necessity for anyone who operates in the world as it actually is: a world in which the boundaries between the political and the commercial, the diplomatic and the transactional, the strategic and the everyday, are not solely porous but are, in truth, illusions sustained only by the convenient fictions of disciplinary separation.

Therefore, that insight is what drove me toward Lorot's text and what made the act of translating it feel like something more than an academic exercise, it was more like closing a loop between experience and reflection, and it is from this closed loop that the remainder of this chapter proceeds: moving outward from the personal to the disciplinary, to the question of what it means, in the twenty-first century, to be a translator.

II. POLITICAL LITERACY: A Professional Imperative

The translator is not a passive conduit through which meaning flows unchanged from one language to another. The translator is an active agent of interpretation, whose choices — at every level from the lexical to the syntactic to the rhetorical — are simultaneously linguistic and political.

— Lawrence Venuti, *The Translator's Invisibility* (1995)

2.1 The Myth of the Neutral Translator

One of the most enduring, most damaging myths in the popular conception of translation is that of the neutral translator: the ideal mediator who stands outside both languages and both cultures, sets aside all ideological commitment, and simply transfers meaning from one side to the other with perfect fidelity and perfect transparency. This translator is imagined as a kind of intelligent instrument — more sophisticated than a dictionary, but essentially of the same order.

This myth is dangerous, precisely because it contains a grain of truth. A good translation does indeed aspire to fidelity. The translator's personal opinions, stylistic preferences, and political convictions should not, in principle, be imposed on a text whose author had different convictions. Yet, the myth is fatally incomplete, because it ignores the foundational reality of translation: that every linguistic choice is simultaneously a cultural, interpretive, and, when relevant, a political choice. When a diplomatic communiqué is translated, the precise rendering of a particular term can determine whether a peace process advances or collapses. When an international treaty is translated, the choice between two near-synonyms can generate decades of legal dispute. When a political speech is translated, the selection of a particular rhetorical register can determine whether a foreign audience receives the speaker as statesman or demagogue.

In all of these cases, and in countless less dramatic but no less consequential instances, the translator who lacks political literacy is not a neutral instrument: they are an inadvertent agent of distortion. Thus, they do not stand outside politics; they blunder through it, unaware of the mines they may be stepping on.

To translate is to make a political choice, whether or not one knows it.

— Georges Mounin, *Les Problèmes théoriques de la traduction* (1963)

2.2 Political Literacy Defined

To be politically literate, as the term is used here, is not to hold political opinions, it rather is an analytical competence: the capacity to understand how power operates at the international level; how states, institutions, and non-state actors pursue interests through the instruments available to them; how language is used to advance, obscure, or contest those interests; and how the meaning of a term or a phrase cannot be fully grasped without understanding the political context in which it was produced and the one in which it will be received.

Political literacy, in this sense, is not a partisan position. It is an **epistemological requirement**.

The experience that motivated this thesis makes the point in the most direct way possible. My inability to close sales in the Middle East during a period of Iranian military strikes was not a failure of commercial technique. It was a consequence of geopolitical reality. Understanding that reality — why states act as they do, what interests drive their behaviour, how military actions translate into economic risk and commercial paralysis — is not a supplement to professional competence in any field that operates across borders. It is a precondition of it.

For the translator, who operates across borders by definition, this precondition is all the more **absolute**.

III. RAISING THE BAR: Saving the Specialty

Languages are the pedigree of nations.

— Samuel Johnson

3.1 Entry Standards

The prevailing curriculum model in most countries treats translation studies as a programme that requires demonstrated linguistic competence in at least two languages and a general academic aptitude — the same baseline that most humanities degrees require. Political knowledge, legal literacy, economic understanding, and technological fluency are treated as assets if possessed but not as requirements.

This model made sense in an era when translation was understood primarily as a linguistic task: a sophisticated exercise in finding the right words in one language for the words of another. It however makes decreasing sense in an era when translation is understood as a complex act of cultural and political mediation, in which linguistic competence is necessary but not sufficient,

and in which the translator's knowledge of the world being described in the text is at least as important as their knowledge of the language in which it is described

Raising the entry requirements for translation studies does not mean making it a more elite or exclusive discipline. It contributes to making it a more honest one about what the work actually demands and what it takes to be a successful translator, by addressing the gap between the preparation that current programmes provide and the preparation that the contemporary world requires, and overcoming it.

3.2 Curriculum Reform

A curriculum that is adequate to the demands of the contemporary world, would look substantially different from the prevailing model. It would retain, and indeed deepen, its commitment to the rigorous, systematic development of the linguistic competencies that remain the indispensable foundation of translatorial skill, and additionally surround that linguistic core with a set of integrated disciplinary modules designed to provide the contextual knowledge without which linguistic skill cannot fully function.

These modules would crucially include: an introduction to Political Science and International Relations (providing the conceptual vocabulary of the international system and an understanding of the key geopolitical dynamics of the contemporary world); a module on international law and legal translation (covering the basics of public international law and the specific demands of legal translation in diplomatic and commercial contexts); a module on area studies (requiring students to develop specialised knowledge of at least one major world region beyond the language areas in which they are training); and a module on digital literacy and machine translation (providing a critical understanding of AI-assisted translation, Software Localization, and all professional implications of the digital transformation of the field).

This is not an unrealistic vision. It actually is a description of the kind of interdisciplinary breadth that the best translation programmes in the world, at institutions such as the Monterey Institute of International Studies, the *École Supérieure d'Interprètes et de Traducteurs* in Paris, or the Faculty of Translation and Interpreting in Geneva, already aspire to, and that the evidence of professional practice confirms as necessary. The question is not whether this vision is achievable, but whether the discipline has the institutional will to pursue it systematically, rather than leaving it to the initiative of individual programmes or individual students.

3.3 Saving the Specialty

The word ‘saving’ in the final phrase of this chapter’s subtitle is deliberately strong, and it deserves to be defended. Translation as a human profession is under genuine pressure — from the increasing quality and accessibility of machine translation systems, from the economic logic that makes automated translation attractive to clients who prioritise cost over nuance, and from the broader cultural devaluation of linguistic and cultural expertise that the digital age has, in some quarters, encouraged. The response to this pressure cannot be denial: the machines are not going away, and their capabilities will continue to improve. Nor can it be mere defensiveness: the argument that human translation is better because it is human, advanced without evidence, is not an argument that will persuade clients, employers, or policymakers.

The response must be a clear, confident, and evidence-based articulation of what human translation at its highest level provides that machine translation cannot: deep cultural and political intelligence; the capacity to navigate texts whose meaning depends on understanding contexts that are not encoded in training data; the rhetorical sophistication required to handle high-register texts in domains where a mistranslation has consequences that extend far beyond the loss of a sale; and the professional accountability that comes with expertise, identity, and the capacity to explain and defend one’s choices.

This is not a modest claim. Human translation, at the level of genuine expert practice, is one of the most intellectually demanding professions in existence, requiring mastery of at least two languages at a level that very few people achieve naturally, combined with the depth of cultural, political, legal, economic, and technical knowledge that characterises expertise in those domains, combined further with the analytical and rhetorical capacities required to mediate between worldviews at the level of the text. A discipline that trains people to this standard is a discipline that can defend its value against the encroachments of automation. One that settles for less is inevitably training people for obsolescence. The obvious difference between aspiration and reality is the reason why action needs to be very soon taken in the matter.

Final Statement

My thesis began with a missile barrage over the Middle East and a sales meeting that could not happen. It ends with a plea — addressed to the institutions that train translators, to the academics who design their curricula, to the policymakers who set the standards for entry into the profession, and to the students who will become the next generation of linguistic mediators — to take seriously the full complexity of what the translator's work demands.

The world does not stop being political when a translator opens a text. Thus, a translator who understands this and brings to the text not only linguistic mastery but the political, cultural, and analytical intelligence that the text requires is not just better than the rest, they are more honest.

Knowing how to take good advantage of technology rather than denying or escaping it is a fundamental skill language specialists should all acquire. Artificial Intelligence will never replace us if we weaponise it rather than demonise it or fully rely on it. We should understand how to mindfully use the machine. This is a fact that all translators should be aware of.

Translation is no longer as simple of a discipline as it used to be. And in order to keep the profession active, realizing what it takes to pursue it is everyone's responsibility.

Concretely, in a world where words are the instruments of power and the medium through which human beings negotiate their differences, honesty about the demands of the craft is not a virtue.

It is a **must**.

Machines translate words. We translate arguments, contexts, histories, and silences, and know, at every step, the difference between what was said and what could be said. Ideally achieving that takes having a rigorous foundation

GLOSSARY

A - Geopolitics, Geoeconomics and International Relations

TERM	DEFINITION
Geoeconomics	The analysis of economic strategies (notably commercial) decided by states to protect their national economy, acquire mastery of key technologies, or conquer market segments, insofar as such possession confers power and international influence. Term introduced to French scholarship by Pascal Lorot (1997).
Geopolitics	A method that identifies and analyses conflictual phenomena and strategies centred on possession of territory, examined through the influences of the geographical environment, the political arguments of the protagonists, and the continuities of history (Lacoste, 1993).
Soft Power	The ability of a state to achieve desired outcomes through attraction and persuasion rather than coercion or payment. Concept coined by Joseph S. Nye Jr. Distinguished from hard (military/economic) power; increasingly central to post-Cold War geopolitical analysis.
Conflictualité	French abstract mass noun denoting the systemic disposition toward conflict (the regime or structural quality of being conflictual) rather than any specific conflict event. Rendered in English as ‘conflict’ with acknowledged semantic narrowing.
Puissance	A key polysemous French term spanning all ‘power’, ‘strength’, and ‘capacity’. In IR discourse, it denotes the ability to achieve outcomes on the international stage. Appears in compounds: puissance de feu (firepower), volonté de puissance (will to power), puissance publique (sovereign public authority).
Puissance Publique	The formal sovereign authority of the state to act with binding authority. An institutional term of art in French administrative and constitutional law, distinct from l’État (the political entity) and le gouvernement (the executive organ). Rendered as ‘public authority’ or ‘the state’ depending on context.

TERM	DEFINITION
Rayonnement	The outward diffusion of cultural, political, or economic influence from a state. Carries connotations of radiating presence and prestige. Closely linked to the concept of ‘rayonnement de la France’. Functionally translated as ‘influence’ or ‘international standing’, though neither captures the emanating quality of the original.
The Triad	Term popularised by Kenichi Ohmae, designating the three dominant post-Cold War economic blocs: America, Western Europe, and Japan. In active use in French geopolitical and economic discourse during the 1990s.
Asian Dragons	Journalistic shorthand for the high-growth East Asian economies (South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore). The French ‘dragons asiatiques’ is preferred over the English ‘Asian tigers’ in Lorot’s text, as the dragon metaphor connotes power and mythological force.
Economic Warfare	The use of economic instruments as weapons in interstate competition. Lorot distinguishes it from geoeconomics: economic warfare can include the most aggressive and unilateral measures, whereas geoeconomic strategies generally remain within internationally acceptable competitive bounds.
Zero-Sum Game	A competitive framework in which one actor’s gain is equivalent to another’s loss; the total benefit among participants remains constant. Contrasted with positive-sum (win-win) dynamics. Lorot uses it to describe the increasingly adversarial perception of globalised free trade by the late 1990s.
Positive-Sum Game	A competitive framework in which all parties can gain simultaneously, as in cooperative trade under classical liberal economic theory. Described by Lorot as the earlier perception of free trade, since displaced by a zero-sum logic amid intensifying global competition.
Political Literacy	As defined in this thesis: the analytical competence to understand how power operates at the international level; how states, institutions, and non-state actors pursue interests through available instruments; and how language is used to advance, obscure, or contest those interests. Argued to be a professional imperative for translators operating across national and cultural boundaries.

B - Translation and Linguistics

TERM	DEFINITION
Domestication	A translation strategy that adapts source-language content to the norms and expectations of the target culture, rendering the text fluent and natural for target readers. Opposed to foreignisation. Associated with Lawrence Venuti's critique of 'the translator's invisibility'.
Foreignisation	A translation strategy that preserves the foreignness and cultural specificity of the source text, resisting assimilation into target-culture norms. Advocated by Lawrence Venuti as a means of exposing the constructedness of translation and respecting the source culture's difference.
Dynamic Equivalence	A translation principle (Eugene Nida) seeking to produce in target-language readers an effect equivalent to that produced in source-language readers, even if this requires departing from literal fidelity. Contrasted with formal equivalence.
Formal Equivalence	A translation principle that prioritises structural and lexical correspondence between source and target text, preserving grammatical forms, word order, and surface-level features, at the potential cost of naturalness in the target language.
Back-Translation	The process of translating a text that is itself already a translation of an original in the target language. In this thesis, Lorot's French quotations of Luttwak's English work required back-translation, creating epistemological complexity at three removes from the original.
False Friend (Faux Ami)	A word or expression that resembles a term in another language but differs significantly in meaning, usage, or register. Example: 'puissance publique' ≠ 'public power'; 'géo-économie' used as a count noun ≠ 'geoeconomics' as an abstract field name.
Calque	A loan translation in which the morphological structure or idiom of a source-language expression is reproduced element by element in the target language. Example: 'patriotisme économique' → 'economic patriotism'. Can risk importing source-culture connotations unchanged.
Neologism	A newly coined word or expression, or an established word used with a new meaning: 'géoéconomie' / 'geoeconomics' (Luttwak, 1990; Lorot, 1997); 'espace fluidifié' / 'fluidified space'. Translating neologisms requires decisions on hyphenation, morphological transparency, and target-language coinages.
Register	The variety of language appropriate to a particular social situation, purpose, or audience — including choices of vocabulary, syntax, and tone.

TERM	DEFINITION
	Managing register across languages is a core translation competency; misregister (e.g., rendering a formal French manifesto in casual English) distorts the source text's meaning and authority.
Nominalisation	The process of converting verbs or adjectives into nouns, producing abstract noun phrases. A marked feature of French academic prose (e.g., 'la marginalisation du facteur militaro-stratégique'). Translating into English may require converting nominalisations back to verbal or adjectival constructions for idiomatic readability.
TMS (Translation Management System)	Software platform used to manage the full workflow of translation projects, including version control, terminology management, translator assignment, and quality assurance. Examples cited in this thesis: Phrase (formerly Memsource), Lokalise, Crowdin.

C - Software Localisation and Technology

TERM	DEFINITION
CAT Tool	Computer-Assisted Translation tool: software that aids human translators through translation memory (storing previously translated segments), glossary lookup, and alignment tools. Distinct from fully automated machine translation.
App Localisation (L10n)	The adaptation of a software application to the linguistic, cultural, typographic, and functional expectations of a target market. Goes beyond translation of UI strings to encompass RTL layout, date/number formatting, culturally appropriate iconography, and UX copy adapted to local dialect and register.
Internationalisation (i18n)	The technical process of designing a software application so that it can be adapted to multiple languages and regions without engineering changes. Involves extracting all hardcoded strings into locale files and enabling runtime language switching.
RTL (Right-to-Left)	A text directionality used by Arabic, Hebrew, Persian, and other scripts. RTL localisation requires structural inversion of UI layout: navigation, alignment, icons, and input fields must all be mirrored. Requires framework-level support (e.g., React Native RTL, iOS UISemanticContentAttribute, Android LayoutDirection).
Unicode BIDI Algorithm	The Unicode Bidirectional Algorithm, which governs how text of mixed directionality (left-to-right and right-to-left) is displayed within a single interface. Critical for Arabic or Hebrew apps that also display Latin numerals or English brand names.

D - Business and Professional Practice

TERM	DEFINITION
MSA (Modern Standard Arabic)	The standardised, literary form of Arabic used in formal writing, journalism, and official communication across the Arab world. Distinguished from regional colloquial dialects. For software localisation targeting professional B2B users, MSA is typically preferred for UI copy.
SaaS	Software as a Service: a software distribution model in which applications are hosted in the cloud and provided to users over the internet on a subscription basis. DoorKnock Pro operates as a SaaS platform serving field sales organisations.
PLG (Product-Led Growth)	A go-to-market strategy in which the product itself — rather than sales or marketing teams — is the primary driver of customer acquisition, conversion, and expansion. Relies on in-product viral mechanics, freemium tiers, and network effects.
MRR / ARR	Monthly Recurring Revenue / Annual Recurring Revenue: key financial metrics in subscription businesses measuring predictable, recurring revenue. $ARR = MRR \times 12$. Used in financial projections throughout the DoorKnock Pro business model document.
CAC / LTV	Customer Acquisition Cost / Lifetime Value: paired metrics assessing the sustainability of a SaaS growth model. CAC is the total cost to acquire one customer; LTV is the total revenue that customer generates over the relationship. A healthy SaaS business typically targets $LTV:CAC \geq 3$.
D2D (Door-to-Door) Sales	A field sales methodology in which sales representatives visit potential customers at their homes or businesses directly, without a prior appointment. DoorKnock Pro is designed specifically to support and digitise D2D and broader field sales operations.
MENA	Middle East and North Africa: a geographically and economically significant region encompassing over 420 million Arabic speakers.
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council: a political and economic union comprising Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates.
Cold Outreach	Unsolicited communication with potential customers who have no prior relationship with the seller, typically via email sequences or telephone calls.

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